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Populist Discourse Online: Islamophobic Themes and Linguistic Markers

Work package 1– Deliverable 1.3

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1. Executive Summary

This report is organised into two main components: a literature review and an empirical study.

The aim of the literature review is to examine the types of discourse used in online discussions about migration and ethnic minorities, with a particular focus on negative, harmful or divisive narratives. These include forms of extreme or polarising communication such as hate speech, Islamophobia, populist rhetoric, xenophobia, racism, toxic framing, disinformation and misinformation. Within this broader framework, the report critically examines representations of Muslims in migration as documented in the existing literature.

The second section presents the Italian case study, which focuses on the discourses of Italian Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) elected in the 2024 European elections as manifested in their short message posts on the Instagram platform. Italy represents a particularly relevant case for analysing how Islam is discursively constructed in political communication, especially by far-right actors. The study examines Instagram posts, mainly from members of the “Lega” (Italian far-right party), to understand how Islam and Muslim migrants are discursively represented, hereby considering the communicative strategies required by the platform such as “hooks” (brief opening phrases designed to capture attention and encourage continued engagement) and “calls to action” (short prompts at the end that encourage people to interact, like commenting, liking or sharing). The dataset was collected on 22 January 2026 using the “Meta Content Library” (a Meta tool used to explore, analyse and collect content across Meta platforms like Instagram and Facebook), including public accounts with more than 25,000 followers. This report presents preliminary results based on a manual, in-depth analysis of the first 100 posts, allowing for a detailed qualitative examination.

To analyse the data, a mixed-methods research design was applied, combining computational text analysis (topic modelling) with qualitative thematic and rhetorical-linguistic analysis.

- 1) The thematic analysis shows that Islam is not presented in a neutral or descriptive way, but is constructed as a culturally incompatible, security-relatedly and socially problematic phenomenon. Through selective language, moral evaluations and oppositions between “us” and “them,” Islam is framed as a widespread and growing threat, visible in everyday contexts and linked to broader political and cultural concerns. Within this framework, hooks play a key role in capturing attention and shaping interpretation, often presenting Islam as an urgent and alarming concern. At the same time, calls to action encourage audiences to react, take a position and engage. This analysis considers content not as a mere reflection of reality, but as part of a broader communicative strategy through which meanings, categories and power relations are constructed. From this perspective, Instagram posts actively contribute to the definition, classification and politicisation of Islam.
- 2) The rhetorical-linguistic analysis combines multiple perspectives. An examination of verb choices (“transitivity”) across a non-left-wing ethnic Italian in-group, an Italian and European left-wing out-group, and a Muslim out-group shows that in-group actors are represented as meritorious, active and publicly engaged, particularly in opposing or preventing the establishment of Islamic institutions. The left-wing out-group is framed as weak, complicit, and responsible for accommodating Islamic practices, while the Muslim out-group is depicted as highly active in imposing norms and opposing Western culture, with processes described as rapid, large-scale and persistent. Processes of verbalisation tied to this group further attribute significant “voice” to it. The distribution of varying modal verbs portrays the in-group as constrained by external necessities imposed by the two out-groups, whereas the latter are

represented as acting freely and strategically. Exclamations and emotionally loaded language combine urgency with blame, consistently directed at out-groups. References to large numbers contribute to framing immigration as a significant and costly issue. Questions to the audience appear limited in use, while exhortations are more frequent, though primarily confined to online engagement and often vague in terms of actors and actions, with no clear indication of incitement to concrete offline behaviour.

Together, the findings of the literature review and the Italian case study converge in showing that the discourse on Islam and Muslim migrants is not neutral, but structured through recurring patterns that combine thematic content, linguistic choices and platform-specific communication strategies.

2. About DEMINE

DEMINE goals

Globalisation and immigration have altered intercommunity relations, leading to a rise in intergroup conflict marked by discrimination against diverse minorities. This has given way to various forms of radicalisation and extremism, spanning religious, political, and xenophobic spectrums worldwide. Globalisation and immigration strain social cohesion (shared public values, group norms, guiding principles) in numerous countries. While individual attitudes may not have shifted significantly, the prominence of migration in public discourse and the polarisation of public opinion have increased substantially. As a result, a divided public opinion has become more overtly hostile towards migration.

The DEMINE (DEaling with conflicts related to MIgration: NEgotiating social cohesion through communication) European Joint Doctorate (DN-JD) network is a collaborative effort across disciplines. Its primary goal is to enhance Europe's capacity to address a significant challenge: the rise of various forms of radicalisation and extremism that pose a threat to social cohesion. Through a combination of inter-sectoral mobility and a balanced blend of research and transferable competences, DEMINE develops a much-needed framework on the role and interplay of interpersonal and mediated communication in intergroup relations and conflict related to migration and globalisation, ultimately contributing to social cohesion. DEMINE has crafted a comprehensive research and training programme to examine the complex relationships between various forms of communication, including traditional media, social media, and interpersonal interactions. This programme aims to understand how various communication channels shape individual attitudes and beliefs regarding migration, as well as their impact on intergroup dynamics (social cohesion), especially within the broader context of political and societal polarisation, and the processes of radicalisation, with a specific focus on migration-related aspects.

DEMINE Educational Goals

- Train nine doctoral candidates to become the next generation of interdisciplinary researchers skilled in digital methods, participatory community research and the evaluation of intergroup conflicts.
- Equip candidates with advanced theoretical and practical knowledge, focusing on strategic analysis, community-based participatory youth work and open-source intelligence techniques.
- Develop transferable skills such as self-management, inter-sectoral collaboration and innovation-oriented thinking to prepare candidates for both academic and non-academic careers.

- Promote interdisciplinary and international mobility, enabling candidates to apply their research findings in real-world contexts and contribute to professional fields ranging from strategic analysis to media production.

DEMINE Research Goals

- Identify and analyse the differences and similarities across various forms of socially unacceptable, extreme discourse, particularly related to migration, at the intersections of politics, media and interpersonal communication.
- Investigate the impact of extreme discourse on individual attitudes and beliefs, with a specific focus on adolescents and vulnerable populations, while understanding the socio-demographic and psychological factors influencing susceptibility.
- Develop countermeasures to empower adolescents, news media producers, and political actors to mitigate the societal impact of divisive discourse, fostering social cohesion and reinforcing democratic principles.
- Provide a nuanced, cross-cultural, and interdisciplinary understanding of the mechanisms of polarisation and radicalisation to inform effective strategies and policy interventions.

By integrating these educational and research goals, DEMINE aims to enhance Europe's capacity to address the growing societal challenges linked to migration, fostering resilience and inclusivity in an increasingly polarised world.

DEMINE Consortium

DEMINE consists of three academic partners namely, KU Leuven, Aarhus Universitet, and Università Degli Studi di Padova as well as nine non-academic partners including OCAM-OCAD, City of Mechelen, Textgain, The Migration Policy Group, Refugees Welcome, Institut for Menneskerettigheder, Stichting Bellingcat, Verwey-Jonker Institute and Hannah Arendt Institute.

The DEMINE consortium is training nine doctoral candidates (DCs) within a cross-disciplinary and international environment, giving them the opportunity to network, study and collect data in Western, Northern, Southern and Eastern Europe (see secondments) in collaboration with academic and non-academic experts, with ample opportunities to develop transferable skills such as technology literacy, adaptability (i.e., not feeling helpless in the face of change), strong communication skills and ability to work in a team, in a dependable and well-organised fashion.

3. Introduction

This report outlines a comprehensive methodology for collecting and annotating social media data with the aim of identifying linguistic markers in populist discourses targetting Muslim migrant populations in Italy. It details the development of an analytical framework capable of systematically capturing recurring thematic, linguistic and rhetorical patterns that characterise such discourse, particularly where it intersects with hatred and discrimination.

The analysis pays specific attention to key features of populist communication, including divisive framing and message simplification, which frequently incorporate Islamophobic narratives targetting Muslim migrant communities. Rather than treating Islamophobic narratives as a monolithic category, it examines its principal linguistic markers, such as choice of verbs for ascribing activities presented as negative, persistent and goal-directed, modal expressions for ascribing a large permission field for and blamefulness of the Islamic population, descriptions designed to activate negative emotions, and the use of large numbers for ascribing urgency and costliness for the host country, while unpacking their semantic and social dimensions to avoid reductive interpretations.

The report concludes by translating these analytical insights into practical recommendations for moderators and policymakers. It encourages the integration of the proposed framework into content moderation practices and public policy design, with the aim of supporting more nuanced, context-sensitive strategies to address harmful populist and Islamophobic discourse online.

4. Literature Reviews

4.1 Scoping review: Extreme discourse on migration and Muslims

The scoping review aims to examine the types of language and communication, referred to as discourse, used in discussions about migration and ethnic minorities, with a particular focus on narratives that are negative, harmful, or divisive. These include forms of extreme, radical, hate-filled, or polarising discourse, such as hate speech, Islamophobia, populist rhetoric, xenophobia, racism, toxic framing, disinformation and misinformation. In addition to identifying these discursive patterns, the review seeks to map the key actors, institutions and platforms involved in producing and disseminating such discourse, including politicians, media organisations, online influencers and social media platforms. Furthermore, it investigates the societal impacts and consequences of these narratives as well as the factors that shape susceptibility or resilience among individuals and groups.

Studies were included if they addressed migration-related discourse and focused on at least one of the following aspects: the linguistic and rhetorical characteristics of harmful or extreme content (such as racist tropes, dehumanising metaphors or fear-based narratives), or the predictors of and susceptibilities to exposure to or acceptance of such content. Relevant contexts included media, education, social media, public communication, and political discourse. Conversely, studies were excluded if they consisted solely of literature reviews (including systematic reviews and scoping reviews), if they were published only as conference proceedings, or if they were written in languages other than English. Additional exclusion criteria applied to studies that did not focus on harmful or divisive discourse in a migration-related context, as well as those that did not concern human migration or the experiences of ethnic minorities.

Within this broader context, the case of Muslims in migration-related extreme discourse stands out as particularly revealing in the scoping review. Muslims are rarely examined as a distinct religious

category in a narrowly theological sense. Instead, they are predominantly approached as a target of exclusionary, threat-based and othering discourse embedded within migration debates (Woodbridge et al., 2025; Abbas, 2020). The same terminological patterns identified in the overall corpus—dehumanising language, migration framing, affective expressions and discursive strategies—are especially salient in the Muslim-related subsample (Yazdiha, 2020; Gorman & Culcasi, 2020). This suggests that Muslims are best understood as positioned at the intersection of migration discourse and racialised-religious boundary-making, rather than as a clearly delineated, religion-oriented field with a stable conceptual vocabulary of its own (Sufi & Yasmin, 2022; Nilan et al., 2025).

The absence of standardised terminology is particularly significant in this regard. Studies rarely converge on labels such as “anti-Muslim discourse” or “Islamophobia in migration discourse,” instead capturing overlapping phenomena through broader categories such as racism, populism, hate speech and othering (Ait Abdeslam, 2021; Sablina, 2019). As a result, Muslims often appear in the literature indirectly, embedded within narratives of migrant threat, cultural incompatibility or national boundary-making—a dynamic that can be described as conceptual absorption (Groglopo et al., 2025; Vallo et al., 2020). This pattern is further reinforced by the methodological orientation of the field, which prioritises interpretive approaches focused on how Muslims are discursively constructed as a problem, a threat, or an outsider category, rather than on measuring the effects of such constructions (González-Baquero et al., 2023; Cureton & Aguinaldo, 2023).

Representations of Muslims are studied primarily through language about them, with limited attention to visual or multimodal dimensions such as iconography, dress markers or audiovisual assemblages. Although some studies have begun to address this by looking at political imagery and gendered symbols (Doerr, 2021; Kulz & Rashid, 2025), textual analysis remains the primary entry point. Similarly, the discourse analysed is typically drawn from publicly visible arenas, such as social media, political communication and news media (Shayegh et al., 2023; Politzer & Olmos Alcaraz, 2023), while less visible forms of communication remain underexamined. Definitions of anti-Muslim discourse are rarely explicit, with most studies relying on indicators such as threat framing, stereotyping, moralised language or delegitimising labels (Bleich et al., 2022; Awan et al., 2024). This results in blurred boundaries between anti-Muslim discourse, xenophobia, racism and anti-immigration discourse.

Building on these patterns, the Muslim/migration subsample can be analytically organised into four overlapping discursive clusters:

- **Muslims as a threat:** associated with security, crime and demographic anxiety (Woodbridge et al., 2025; Politzer & Olmos Alcaraz, 2023);
- Muslims as outsiders, framed through cultural incompatibility and non-belonging (Groglopo et al., 2025; Nilan et al., 2025);
- **Muslims as undeserving migrants:** constructed through delegitimation and narratives of welfare abuse or comparative “worthiness” (Palmgren et al., 2023; Sheikh, 2021);
- **Muslims as contaminants:** represented through dehumanisation and exclusionary rhetoric (Sablina, 2019; Cockbain & Tufail, 2020).

These categories frequently co-occur, producing layered representations in which Muslims are simultaneously constructed as dangerous, alien, morally suspect and socially undesirable. Two broader observations emerge from this: first, a strong convergence of discursive logics, whereby threat, othering, delegitimation and abjection reinforce one another; and second, a persistent conceptual under-specification, as the literature rarely isolates anti-Muslim discourse as a distinct

analytical category, instead subsuming it within broader frameworks (Sufi & Yasmin, 2022; Abbas, 2020).

Overall, these findings suggest that within the broader migration discourse corpus, Muslims are primarily studied through the lenses of othering, threat, and delegitimation, in predominantly empirical, text-based, discourse-analytical research focused on publicly visible communication. However, they are only inconsistently conceptualised as a distinct racialised-religious target, highlighting the need for greater conceptual clarity in future research.

4.2 Instagram communication strategies: Hooks, calls to action and user engagement

The literature increasingly examines the role of Instagram as a communication and marketing tool, highlighting a gradual shift from traditional communication models toward more interactive and participatory digital forms. Several studies underscore the declining effectiveness of conventional media in reaching audiences, favouring social media platforms for their capacity to facilitate immediate, bidirectional and dynamic communication (Larsson, 2021). In this context, the most effective communication strategies are based on the exploitation of Integrated Marketing Communication (IMC) principles, which require message consistency and coordination across channels, as well as on the specific features of social media, such as interactivity, personalisation and real-time feedback (Dwikesumasari et al., 2020).

Within the contemporary digital ecosystem, the effectiveness of content largely depends on the ability to capture users' attention in the very first moments of exposure. In this regard, so-called *hooks* play a central role in content writing, as they determine the transition from simple exposure to active engagement (Zhang et al., 2026; Epstein et al., 2022). The literature shows that short, evocative and sometimes provocative headlines, such as those using questions, emotionally charged words, or urgency cues, are particularly effective in interrupting users' scrolling behaviour and generating immediate interest. This approach aligns with the first stage of the AISAS model (Attention, Interest, Search, Action, Share), which highlights the importance of capturing attention as a prerequisite for any subsequent interaction, both in corporate communication and in journalistic communication (Amalia & Patrissia, 2025). Moreover, effective *hooks* do not only attract attention but also anticipate the informational or emotional value of the content, creating expectations that encourage users to continue engaging with it. In particular, the integration of narrative elements, a conversational tone and emotional appeals in the initial part of the message significantly increase engagement levels (Amalia & Patrissia, 2025).

Another key communication strategy in social media is represented by *calls to action* (CTAs), that is, explicit prompts encouraging users to perform specific actions, such as commenting, sharing, clicking or participating. CTAs play a central role in digital platforms because they transform users from passive viewers into active participants, fostering interaction and co-creation dynamics. However, their effectiveness is not uniform and depends on how they are designed. In particular, CTAs that invite users to engage in activities directly connected to the content or brand, especially when integrated into interactive or playful experiences, tend to be more effective, as they are more engaging, clear and consistent with the overall message (Pletikosa Cvijikj & Michahelles, 2013; De Vries et al., 2012; Tafesse, 2016). In contrast, CTAs based on simple requests for opinions or conversation, as well as those offering rewards, tend to generate lower levels of engagement, especially in content related to social responsibility, where users value authenticity and relevance (Chae, 2021). Furthermore, the excessive presence of multiple CTAs within the same message may reduce engagement, making

communication less clear and more fragmented. Overall, an effective CTA should be simple, targeted and consistent with the content so as to stimulate immediate and meaningful participation (Chae, 2021).

Complementing these attention mechanisms, CTAs can also be understood as explicit or implicit prompts that guide users toward specific forms of engagement, such as liking, commenting, sharing or clicking (Poggi, 2007; Lee & Hong, 2016). Research shows that CTAs function as behavioural triggers, directly influencing user actions and, in some cases, even impulsive behaviours (Setiawan & Savitri, 2019). However, their effectiveness depends on strategic use: excessive or poorly integrated CTAs can reduce engagement, whereas well-calibrated prompts enhance interaction and participation (Kim & Johnson, 2016). In addition, the design of CTAs on Instagram tends to favour brevity, clarity and emotional resonance, in line with the platform's fast-paced and visually oriented communication environment (Rahmawati, 2020).

Overall, the literature suggests that effective communication on Instagram is structured around the interaction between attention (*hooks*) and activation (CTAs), forming a core mechanism that drives user engagement. Importantly, these strategies are not limited to commercial or branding contexts, but also apply to broader communicative domains, including political communication, persuasive messaging and potentially harmful or polarising discourse. In such cases, emotionally charged hooks and directive CTAs may amplify the visibility and circulation of content, highlighting the importance of considering these mechanisms in the analysis of contemporary digital discourse (Ashley & Tuten, 2015; De Veirman et al., 2017).

In line with this perspective, recent literature on political communication on Instagram shows that strategies related to hooks and CTAs are central to the structuring of political content, even when they are not explicitly labelled as such. Empirical studies demonstrate that a significant share of political content includes forms of direct audience activation; for instance, analyses of election-related communication on Instagram indicate that approximately half of posts contain explicit CTAs aimed at encouraging behaviours such as sharing, participation or voting (Achmann-Denkler et al., 2024). At the same time, political communication widely relies on implicit activation strategies based on visual and emotional content that function as hooks, capturing attention and fostering engagement. In this regard, the rise of Instagram as a political communication tool has been accompanied by an increasing use of visually salient and emotionally charged content, which is particularly effective in generating interaction, especially among populist actors (Larsson, 2021).

At the same time, several studies highlight the role of personalisation and narrative construction as key elements of these strategies. The representation of candidates in informal settings, the use of positive imagery and the creation of an emotional connection with the audience act as narrative hooks that promote identification and engagement (de Lima-Santos et al., 2024). Similarly, case-based analyses show that narrative coherence, emotional appeal and personalisation contribute to building relationships with the electorate, activating forms of participation that can be interpreted as implicit CTAs (Sandes & Carriço Reis, 2025). Research on populist communication further indicates that emotionally intense and simplified messages function as mechanisms of audience activation, encouraging interaction and content diffusion without necessarily relying on explicit calls to action (Messini, 2025).

Finally, studies on political interaction dynamics on the platform show that political content is inherently designed to stimulate active responses from users, generating high levels of commenting,

discussion, and participation, even in the absence of explicit CTAs (Trevisan et al., 2021). Overall, these findings suggest that political communication on Instagram is based on a hybrid model in which attention strategies (*hooks*) and activation strategies (CTAs) operate together, contributing to the maximisation of visibility, engagement and mobilisation. These dynamics are particularly relevant in the context of polarising or extreme discourse, where the combined use of emotionally salient content and activation mechanisms—both explicit and implicit—can amplify the spread and impact of divisive narratives.

4.3 Theoretical prerequisites for rhetorical and linguistic analysis

4.3.1. Conceptual metaphors

Metaphors (the substitution of one concept for another based on a perceived overlap in meaning, e.g., a “warrior” described as a “lion” to evoke ferocity) have been extensively discussed since Aristotle, who treated them as rhetorical figures of embellishment or persuasion. In this tradition, metaphors were relatively rare in texts and therefore highly salient.

With the introduction, by Lakoff and Johnson (1980), of the notion of *conceptual metaphor*, the take on metaphors has radically changed: metaphors are now seen as omnipresent cognitive phenomena that help us to structure our thought; they are mostly non-salient, because we are used to them. Conceptual metaphors do not replace single concepts with other concepts but work on a more abstract level: they help us understand abstract conceptual domains (like time) by recasting them in terms of concrete domains (e.g., space). These recastings are also called cognitive schemes, and they are usually formalised by (small) capital letters. Lakoff and Johnson (1980) introduced several types: *ontological* metaphors that represent abstract concepts as physical objects, substances or persons (THE MIND IS A COMPUTER; EMOTIONS ARE SUBSTANCES; THE MARKET IS A WILLFUL PERSON), *orientational* metaphors that give spatial orientation to abstract concepts like emotions or value judgments (HAPPY IS UP, SAD IS DOWN; GOOD IS UP, BAD IS DOWN), and finally *structural* metaphors that recast abstract, complex concepts as concrete, structured concepts (ARGUMENT IS WAR; TIME IS A RESOURCE/MONEY; ECONOMIC ACTIVITY IS WAR). These cognitive schemes underpin concrete verbalisations like *I was high after having passed the exam* or *time is running out*, which are not always conspicuous, because they are notably ubiquitous and often also lexicalised.

Conceptual metaphors can, however, also be used to more or less subtly frame actors and situations in a favourable or unfavourable light. Lafiandra (2025, p. 1) is one of many authors describing the use of water metaphors (“waterphores”) for negatively framing immigration, providing examples such as *wave*, *submersion*, and *tide*. Taylor (2021, p. 465) mentions the following conceptual metaphors used to frame immigration in existing research: INVADERS, CRIMINALS, GUESTS (in human form), and WATER, ANIMALS, OBJECTS, BURDEN, WEEDS, POLLUTANTS, COMMODITY, PARASITES, DISEASE and LIQUID (non-human). In our data, the use of the conceptual metaphor IMMIGRATION IS INVASION/WAR is pervasive.

4.3.2. Transitivity

One of the most important rhetorical tools for discursively framing actors (people or institutions) is “transitivity”, the discursive representation of people “in regard to what they are doing”, a subtle way of shaping other people’s perceptions of the described actors (Machin & Mayr, 2025, chapter 6, p. 2). Based on Halliday (1994), “transitivity” analysis maps who is presented as an active vs. passive participant in a verbal action, and whether the action is “good” or “bad”. Higher activity in good actions (e.g., in grammatical subjects of dynamic verbs) embellishes the merits of an actor, while higher activity in bad actions tarnishes the actor’s persona. Responsibility for bad actions (*The*

president made mistakes) can be downplayed by re-casting the actor in adverbial form in a passive sentence (*Mistakes were made by the president*) or even removing them completely (as in the notorious Bush quote *Mistakes were made*).

In our below transitivity analysis for the actors represented in our data, we follow Halliday's (1994) categories of process types: *material* (doing concrete actions), *mental* (cognitive, affective, perceptive: can create empathy, but can also frame passivity), *verbal* (verbs of saying: having a voice = having power, sometimes too much power), *relational* (*be, have*: allow to present opinions as facts), and *existential* (*exist, happen*: together with nominalisations of actions, agency and responsibility can be obscured) (Machin & Mayr, 2025, chapter 6, p. 4-9).

4.3.3. Modality

In linguistics, modality is defined as “any kind of speaker modification of a state of affairs” (Nuyts, 2006: 1), one could say semantic comments on various aspects of the propositional content of an utterance, like epistemic modality (an assessment of the degree of truth or probability of the proposition) or deontic modality (the permission/prohibition or obligation of a state of affairs). In (Indo-)European languages, these meanings are realised through modal verbs (e.g., *can, must*), adverbs (*probably, maybe*), and adjectives (*sure, forbidden, necessary*).

The French linguistic tradition treats value judgments as a form of modality, distinguishing in particular between appreciative and axiological modality. Appreciative modality expresses the desirability or undesirability of a state or event and reflects the speaker's subjective judgment. Axiological modality, by contrast, concerns the praiseworthiness or blameworthiness of actions and is grounded in institutional norms (Gosselin, 2017). While both axiological and deontic modality relate to normative frameworks, deontic modality is inherently prescriptive, whereas axiological modality can be either prescriptive or descriptive. Another relevant modality is the *boulomaic* one, which is the subjective (of the speaker) and prescriptive expression of willingness or refusal¹. The *boulomaic* and deontic modalities can only apply to future situations, while the appreciative and axiological modalities can also apply to present and past situations (Gosselin, 2017, p. 114)

In their account of modal adjectives, van linden & Verstraate (2011, p. 155) distinguish between weak (*appropriate, convenient, desirable, important, etc.*) and strong (*critical, crucial, essential, indispensable, necessary, needful and vital*) deontic adjectives. In other words, the strong deontic adjective express urgency towards future action.

4.3.4. Speech acts

According to Dirven and Verspoor (2004, p. 151), *speech acts* are “[t]he actual words we utter to realise a communicative intention”. Speech acts relevant for our data are *assertive speech acts* (expressed by declarative sentences), *directive speech acts* (expressed by imperative sentences) and *informative questions* (expressed by interrogative sentences). In assertive utterances “the speaker states what he sees or thinks is happening and informs someone else about this”, informative questions “ask information of the hearer or state that someone lacks a piece of information of some sort”, and in directive utterances, “we give an order [...] or make a request” (Dirven & Verspoor, 2004, p. 151).

4.3.5. Aggregation

“Aggregation” is the strategy of tying high numerical values to actors and thereby treating them as “statistics”, and not as people (Machin & Mayr, 2015, chapter 6, p. 18), which can also result in an

¹ One could say a declaration of intended behavior.

impression of overwhelmingness. Furthermore, high numbers can create a spurious impression of objectivity (Van Dijk, 1991).

5. Italian Case Study

This research study presents the Italian case study, which focuses on the discourses of Italian Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) elected in the 2024 European elections as manifested in their short message posts on the Instagram platform. Italy represents a particularly relevant case for analysing representations of Islam in the popular communication of the Italian parties and political actors.

We compiled a comprehensive list of all Italian MEPs elected for the 2024-2029 term based on official European Parliament election results. In total, 80 elected representatives were identified and manually verified with regard to party affiliation. Data were collected on 22 January 2026 using a downloadable dataset from the Meta Content Library, a tool that enables the exploration, analysis, and collection of content across platforms such as Instagram and Facebook. In this study, it allowed for data collection from public accounts with at least 25,000 followers.

Of the 80 elected Italian MEPs, **57 accounts** met the inclusion criteria and were included in the dataset; the remainder were private, below the follower threshold, or inaccessible via the platform's data access tools at the time of collection (see Appendix 1).

This study addresses several gaps in the literature on discourses about Islam. It shifts attention to underexplored actors—Members of the European Parliament—thereby moving beyond the dominant focus on party leaders and offering a less leader-centric perspective on political communication, particularly in the Italian context.

Thematically, it advances the understanding of how Muslims are positioned within migration discourse by conceptualising anti-Muslim discourse as a distinct subtype of extreme discourse. This approach highlights the intersection of religion, racialisation, and migration status, providing a more precise analytical lens. The study also demonstrates how anti-Islam discourse functions as a component of performative populist political style (Moffitt, 2022), thereby linking discursive content to broader political communication strategies.

Methodologically, the study adopts a mixed-methods approach that combines quantitative and qualitative analysis, integrating thematic and linguistic dimensions. This enables a systematic yet nuanced identification of discursive patterns and allows for the analysis not only of content but also of communicative strategies, such as hooks and calls to action. By combining interpretive depth with analytical precision, the study contributes to a clearer operationalisation of anti-Muslim discourse and a more comprehensive understanding of how polarising narratives are constructed, circulated, and gain traction on platforms such as Instagram.

5.1 Methodology

To examine how Italian Members of the European Parliament (MEPs) construct and frame Islam and migration on Instagram, we implemented a multi-stage mixed-methods research design combining computational text analysis with qualitative thematic and rhetorical-linguistics analysis. Following data collection, the analytical workflow consisted of six sequential steps.

5.1.1 Data cleaning and preprocessing

The dataset was cleaned and standardised. This involved removing duplicate entries, excluding non-textual artifacts (e.g., URLs, excessive emoji strings where necessary), and harmonising metadata fields across accounts. Text data were normalised to facilitate computational analysis, including lowercasing and basic tokenisation procedures. Accounts were annotated with structured metadata, including party affiliation, ideological alignment, and European Parliament group membership, enabling subsequent comparative analyses across political blocs. Prior to topic modelling, all Instagram captions were cleaned and standardised to reduce noise typical of social media data and to improve semantic modelling quality.

First, all texts were converted to lowercase using case folding to ensure uniform lexical representation. Character encoding issues (mojibake) were corrected to restore malformed characters. Diacritics were removed and characters were normalised to ASCII to ensure consistency across Italian language variants. Second, platform-specific artefacts were removed, including URLs and web links, user mentions (@handles), hashtag symbols (while retaining their lexical content), quotation marks and other forms of punctuation, emojis and non-textual Unicode symbols as well as numerical strings. Finally, excess whitespace was normalised to ensure clean token boundaries. These preprocessing steps were designed to preserve semantic content while removing structural noise that could distort embedding-based clustering. The cleaned text corpus served as the input for embedding generation and subsequent BERTopic modelling.

5.1.2 Topic Modelling

To analyse the thematic structure of the Instagram corpus, we employed embedding-based topic modelling. Topic modelling is a computational method designed to identify latent thematic structures within large text collections (Blei et al., 2003). While classical approaches such as Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) rely on bag-of-words assumptions, recent advances integrate contextual embeddings, substantially improving semantic coherence and interpretability (Dieng et al., 2020).

Embedding-based approaches are particularly well suited for short social media texts. Unlike traditional document-based models, they capture semantic similarity beyond surface-level word co-occurrence, account for contextual variation in meaning, and are better equipped to detect implicit references and political framing (Dieng et al., 2020). This is especially relevant for analysing Islam-related discourse, where references may be indirect, symbolic or embedded in broader narratives about migration, identity, or security.

We implemented **BERTopic** (Grootendorst, 2023), a transformer-based topic modelling framework that combines contextual sentence embeddings, dimensionality reduction via UMAP, density-based clustering using HDBSCAN, and class-based TF-IDF (c-TF-IDF) for topic representation. Topic representations were further refined using Maximal Marginal Relevance (MMR) and KeyBERT-inspired keyword extraction to enhance interpretability. BERTopic has been shown to generate coherent and semantically meaningful topics in short-text and multilingual contexts (Axelborn & Berggren, 2023) and has increasingly been applied in communication research to analyse social media storms and media discourse (Berendt & Kiyak, 2026; De Nolf, Kiyak, & d’Haenens, 2026).

Following established mixed methods approaches in computational social science (Bail, 2014; Törnberg & Törnberg, 2016; Isoaho et al., 2021), topic modelling was not treated as a purely

automated classification tool. Instead, topics were manually inspected through keyword lists and representative posts to ensure thematic coherence and substantive validity.

To ensure robustness, multiple BERTopic models with varying embedding architectures and clustering parameters were estimated. The final model, based on the *intfloat/multilingual-e5-large* embedding model, produced 224 topics. Because a substantial number of posts were initially assigned to the outlier cluster, we applied embedding-based outlier reduction, which reassigned content based on semantic similarity in embedding space. This reduced the number of unclustered posts from approximately 26,000 to roughly 3,000, improving topic coverage and stabilising smaller thematic clusters.

5.1.3 Manual identification of Islam-related topics

Following model estimation, topics were manually inspected based on their top keywords and representative posts. Topics explicitly or implicitly related to Islam, Muslims, Islamic practices or Islamisation narratives were identified and flagged for further analysis. This interpretative step ensured that computationally derived clusters were substantively meaningful and aligned with the study's research focus. From the 224-topic model, nine clusters were identified as directly related to Islam, Islamisation, mosques, radicalisation, and gendered religious discourse. Table X presents these topics, including their size and keyword representations across c-TF-IDF, MMR, and KeyBERT extraction (see Appendix 2). Following embedding-based outlier reduction, the Islam-related topics identified through BERTopic comprised 1,642 posts in the corpus.

5.1.4 Keyword-based identification of Islam-related posts

In parallel to topic modelling, we implemented a dictionary-based approach to identify Islam-related discourse across the full corpus. This step was designed to complement the unsupervised model by detecting posts that may not have formed distinct thematic clusters but nonetheless contained explicit references to Islam, Islamic practices or Islam-related political narratives. The keyword list was developed deductively based on prior literature on Islamophobia, securitisation, populist radical-right discourse and civilisational framing. The dictionary was designed to capture four broad categories of references (see Appendix 3). The selected keywords are summarised below and provided with their corresponding English translation:

- **Islam and Muslim identity markers**
(e.g., Islam, Islamic, Muslims, denominations such as Sunni or Shia)
- **Religious practices, institutions, and symbols**
(e.g., mosque, imam, Quran, Ramadan, Eid, hijab, niqab, burqa, halal, sharia)
- **Islamisation and civilisational narratives**
(e.g., Islamisation, radicalisation, fundamentalism, jihadism)
- **Security and terrorism framing linked to Islam**
(e.g., Islamic terrorism, jihad, jihadist, islamophobia)

In addition, gendered religious markers such as *velo* (veil) were included due to their central role in European debates on Islam and women's rights. To ensure comprehensive coverage, the dictionary was implemented using regular expressions (regex) capturing singular and plural forms, gendered variants, common derivations (e.g., *Islamisation*, *radicalisation*), Italian-specific spellings (e.g., *sharia*), and frequent transliteration variants (e.g., *Qur'an/Corano*). All patterns were combined into a single compiled, case-insensitive regex and applied to the cleaned caption text. This approach enabled the

identification of both explicit references (e.g., *mosque, Ramadan, imam*) and broader discursive constructions such as Islamic radicalisation or fundamentalism. Using this procedure, 1,779 posts containing Islam-related terms were identified across the corpus.

5.1.5 Dataset consolidation and manual validation

The outputs of the topic modelling and keyword-matching procedures were then combined. Posts identified by either method were merged into a candidate Islam-related subset. After merging the topic-model-based and keyword-based selections and removing duplicates, the final Islam-related **dataset comprised 2,212 posts**. To increase validity and reduce false positives and false negatives, this subset underwent manual validation. Each post was reviewed to confirm substantive relevance to Islam-related discourse. In this stage each post was coded according to its relevance to the topic of Islam. Specifically, a value of **0** was assigned to posts that were not relevant to the topic, while a value of **1** was assigned to posts that were considered relevant. Out of the initial **2,212 posts, 427 were excluded** (value 0) because they contained misleading keywords or were not actually related to Islam. The remaining **1,785 posts** were therefore retained and classified as relevant to the analysis. In addition, we also analysed a sample of 100 posts excluded from the Islam dataset to confirm false negatives were minimal. The posts contained in this file appear to have been correctly excluded, as none of them were relevant to the discussion on Islam. This step resulted in a curated corpus of Islam-related posts forming the basis of the qualitative analysis.

5.1.6 Qualitative thematic analysis

Before starting the qualitative analysis, this final 1,785 posts were ordered based on the number of “likes” received, with those showing the highest level of engagement appearing first. This approach was adopted because the number of likes can serve as a proxy for the level of interest and engagement expressed by online users.

We conducted an in-depth qualitative thematic discourse analysis (Clarke & Braun, 2013) of the validated Islam-related corpus to identify key emerging themes. In an initial phase, the first 100 posts, selected based on their number of “likes”, were analysed using MaxQDA to support data organisation. Coding was carried out manually through an inductive, interpretative approach, allowing categories to emerge from the data. The analysed content originates predominantly from right-wing political actors, particularly members of the far-right party Lega Nord. The coding process led to the identification of a complex, multi-layered system of coded segments (n = 857), distributed across different analytical dimensions (see Appendix 4). First, themes emerge relating to the construction of Islam in connection with national and cultural identity, the perception of threat, exclusionary positions and political critique. These are accompanied by evaluative and emotional dimensions, such as moral judgment, negative evaluations, and expressions of indignation.

A further level concerns discursive and rhetorical aspects, including the use of metaphors and platform-specific communicative strategies typical of Instagram, such as initial “hooks” and “call-to-action” elements aimed at capturing attention and stimulating interaction. Finally, the discourse is situated within specific contexts through references to places (such as schools or cities), social and political actors and power dynamics. These different dimensions do not operate in isolation but intersect and reinforce one another. The construction of threat is often accompanied by negative evaluations and expressions of indignation, while exclusionary positions are legitimised through appeals to moral values or humanitarian purposes. At the same time, rhetorical elements such as

metaphors, quantitative emphasis and spatial representations contribute to making the discourse more impactful and alarmist.

5.1.7 Qualitative rhetorical-linguistics analysis

The same first 100 most-liked Instagram posts analysed thematically were chosen as the data material for the analysis of rhetorical-linguistic markers of populist discourse. This analysis was performed in a combined inductive (data-driven) and deductive approach, i.e., guided by concepts from literature from different fields such as text and discourse analysis (e.g., Van Dijk, 1991, Machin & Mayr, 2025), semantics (e.g., Gosselin, 2017; Van linden & Verstraate, 2011; Nuyts, 2006), cognitive linguistics (e.g., Lakoff & Johnson, 1980; Dirven & Verspoor, 2005), as well as political theory (e.g., Mudde, 2000; Moffit & Tourmey, 2013). The data were read and re-read multiple times and manually coded for potential rhetorical and linguistic markers for the conceptual characteristics of populist discourse as discussed in the literature: creation of in-group vs. out-groups, evocation of crisis and urgency, appeal to the people, reference to leader figures, the evocation of hereditary values, rights and costumes under threat and performativity. The multiple re-reading and re-coding of the data led finally to a list of the most central rhetorical and linguistic phenomena that together constructed the populist discourse as represented in the data: conceptual metaphors, transitivity, modality, speech acts as well as aggregation.

6. Results

6.1. Communicative strategies on Instagram

Two key communicative devices structure communication on Instagram: initial hooks and calls to action (CTAs), which play a central role in shaping how content is framed, perceived, and engaged by audiences. These communicative practices are shaped by the affordances of Instagram, a platform characterised by visual immediacy, rapid scrolling and engagement-driven metrics.

“Hooks” (see above) are used to immediately capture attention and shape the interpretation of the content from the very first words. In this data, this often occurs through emotional and alarmist formulations that present Islam as a threat or as a phenomenon in expansion.

“Calls to action” (see above), in turn, introduce a more active and mobilising dimension by encouraging the audience to react, comment, or take a stance. In this way, the discourse does not simply describe reality but prompts users to participate and align themselves with a particular position.

These strategies not only organise content but also directly shape communicative practices, influencing both the ways messages are constructed and the forms of interaction with audiences. Taken together, they reflect and reinforce platform logics that prioritise visibility and engagement, contributing to the amplification and circulation of simplified and polarising narratives. This highlights the importance of considering platform-specific dynamics in the analysis of contemporary digital political communication.

6.1.1 Initial hooks

In the context of Instagram, a crucial role is played by initial phrases, the so-called hooks, which open posts and immediately establish their interpretative frame. These function as a key strategic device: the opening sentence must capture attention, generate emotional impact and shape the reading of

the content from the outset. In a platform characterised by rapid scrolling, competition for visibility and limited attention spans, hooks operate as entry points into the discourse, condensing the meaning of the post into a few words and predisposing the audience to interpret it in terms of urgency, threat or scandal.

In the analysed dataset, hooks do not introduce Islam in a neutral way, but almost always present it as a sign of spreading phenomenon, imposition or ongoing transformation. Expressions such as *we must fight against Islamisation in our cities; alarming images from Milan: Islamisation is spreading like wildfire; in Vienna, Muslim students are already the majority; or Belgium is already Islamised!* clearly show how Islam is immediately framed as a problem, a threat, or a source of alarm, even before the content is further developed.

This construction unfolds through several recurring strategies. First, Islam is represented as a growing, systemic, and already visible threat, embedded in a dynamic of expansion and acceleration. This is accompanied by its representation as a normative and political force in expansion (*Muslims want to rule us..., Islamic law is making its way into Europe*), together with references to direct threats or the symbolic transformation of urban spaces, all of which reinforce the idea of a danger already in progress.

A further element concerns the localisation of the threat within key institutions, such as schools, hospitals, and courts, suggesting that transformation has already penetrated the spaces where citizenship is formed, and collective values are reproduced. At the same time, everyday symbols and practices—such as the Islamic veil, the Arabic language, or the halal diet—are used as concrete and immediately recognizable signs of a broader cultural transformation, particularly effective in the visual environment of Instagram.

Islamic presence is also made tangible through references to mosques, imams and Islamic centres, presented not merely as places of worship but as indicators of expansion, organisation, and entrenchment. At the same time, certain practices are described as incompatible or offensive, activating an immediate reading in terms of cultural conflict. An important role is also played by the representation of Islam as a threat to women, which moralises the discourse and justifies exclusionary positions in terms of protection. Similarly, the direct association with terrorism, radicalism, and crime reinforces a securitarian frame and presents the phenomenon as a concrete risk.

The dimension of threat is further expanded through references to international contexts, linking the local level to a broader geopolitical scenario such as Belgium, Germany and Vienna. Finally, the use of testimonies and references to the defense of national identity contributes to conferring authenticity and reinforcing defensive framing.

Overall, in the dataset the hooks operate on multiple levels: they capture attention through brief and dramatising formulations, anticipate the narrative frame, and emotionally predispose the audience toward indignation, fear, or a sense of urgency. In this way, they function as discursive devices that guide interpretation from the outset, presenting Islam as a widespread, concrete, and multidimensional threat.

6.1.2 Engaging the public: “Call to Action”

A central component of the discourse concerns its explicitly mobilising dimension. In the analyzed posts, Islam is not only described as a cultural, political, or security threat, but is also presented as a phenomenon in relation to which the audience is called upon to react, take a stance, express

indignation, or support specific measures. In this sense, the discourse assumes a performative function: the post does not merely inform or evaluate but becomes a device for political activation.

In the context of Instagram, this function is particularly significant. The platform privileges content capable of generating immediate interaction—comments, shares, reactions—and mobilising formulations respond perfectly to this logic. Direct questions such as *what do you think?*, imperative expressions such as *look!, listen!, tune in*, or broader exhortations such as *we must react* and *it is time to choose which side to stand on* contribute to reducing the distance between author and audience, transforming the public from passive spectators into engaged subjects.

From a discursive perspective, this means that Islam is constructed not only as a problem, but as an urgent problem requiring a response. These formulations do not necessarily introduce new content but rather orient the interpretation of what has already been presented, pushing the reader toward a political and moral stance.

A first way in which this occurs is through the use of provocative questions, rhetorical interrogatives, and exhortations that prompt immediate reaction. The content is thus organised as provocation rather than as neutral information. Expressions such as *where are the left-wing protests while men and women in Iran are being massacred by the Islamic regime?, and the animal rights activists? do they have nothing to say?, now let us ask ourselves: if it can happen in Belgium, what prevents it from happening here as well?, or why does the European Union waste millions of euros...?* guide the audience toward an implicit response, reinforcing a pre-existing frame: that of passive institutions, political complicity, and an already visible Islamic threat.

In other cases, the provocation takes on a more explicitly mobilising form, as in *it is time to choose which side to stand on. before it is too late or they want to erase us, we must react*. Here, the reader is directly interpellated as a moral subject, placed before a forced choice between passivity and resistance. Islam is thus embedded within a logic of urgency and polarisation: it is not merely an object of discourse, but a matter on which one must take sides.

A second modality concerns the direct appeal to visual or audiovisual content, fully consistent with the nature of Instagram. Formulations such as *look!, listen to these unacceptable statements, have you heard the harsh words of the imam of Bologna?, look at what is happening in Naples, listen to the absurd statements of these Muslims about the Islamic veil, or listen to what the Islamic representative says about women's veils* perform a specific function: they frame the content before it is even consumed.

This is crucial because the audience does not watch or listen in a neutral way. Visual materials—videos, images, testimonies—are preceded by an invitation that directs their meaning, guiding interpretation in terms of scandal, danger, or incompatibility. In this sense, discourse acts as a mechanism of pre-interpretation. Within the platform, this strategy is particularly effective: it interrupts the flow of scrolling and prompts the user to engage directly with the content. Islam is thus constructed not only as a topic, but as something to be seen, heard, and visually verified.

Overall, these strategies perform several complementary functions. On the one hand, they mobilise the audience, interpellating it as a subject called to react (*we must react, it is time to choose*). On the other hand, they foster interactive engagement, encouraging comments and reactions (*what do you think?*). They also guide interpretation, especially in audiovisual posts, through directives such as *look* and *listen*. Finally, they contribute to the polarisation of the discourse, placing the audience before an implicit choice between opposing camps: those who defend identity, security, and freedom, and those who are associated with tolerating or promoting Islamisation.

Within this framework, the mobilising dimension represents a central element of the communicative strategy on Instagram: the discourse does not merely describe reality, but calls for action—commenting, sharing, supporting, expressing indignation—thereby transforming interpretation into participation.

6.2 Result of the thematic analysis

6.2.1 Moral Judgment as the Structuring Principle of Discourse

6.2.1.1 Islam as an object of moral judgment

One of the most significant aspects emerging from the analysis concerns the central role of moral judgment. Islam, the practices associated with it, and the Muslim community are not represented as merely different, but rather as morally problematic, wrong, unacceptable, or incompatible with the principles of the national and European community. In this sense, the discourse is consistently organised around a distinction between what is considered legitimate and what is not, between what belongs to a shared value system and what is instead constructed as a threat.

This dynamic clearly appears in formulations such as *we must fight against Islamisation in our cities... we must do so to defend our identity, our culture, our traditions*, where the reference to Islam is immediately placed within a framework of moral defense of the collective. The issue is not simply that Islam is perceived as different, but that this difference is immediately translated into a problem to be addressed.

The first fundamental aspect of this moralisation concerns the defense of national and cultural identity. In numerous posts, Islam is negatively evaluated insofar as it is discursively represented as incompatible with traditions, symbols, and values perceived as constitutive of the community. Phrases such as *let us defend our civilisation, our values, our freedom, we will defend our history, our roots, and our rights with all our strength, or Italy must be defended... our history, our values, and our freedom are non-negotiable* show how the discourse does not merely condemn something but also serves to define what deserves protection.

Alongside this explicit defense, there also emerges a denunciation of internal identity loss. In this case, the discourse does not only condemn Islam, but also those who are perceived as responsible for relinquishing their own cultural references. Formulations such as *the replacement of our culture, our religion, and our history is proceeding at full speed, yet another abuse of multiculturalist ideology that uses the pretext of coexistence to erase our roots and our identity, or an Italy that is ashamed of its own roots, yet readily accepts the slow and inexorable erasure of its identity* clearly indicate that the moral discourse extends to the stigmatisation of an alleged internal surrender. Islam, therefore, is constructed not only as an external threat, but also as an element that makes visible the moral and cultural failure of those who are deemed incapable of defending the community, with particular reference to the Italian left.

6.2.1.2 Exclusion as a morally justified response

The logic of moral judgment often translates into an explicitly exclusionary stance. In many cases, the rejection of Islam or of practices associated with it is framed as a necessary and legitimate ethical position. Phrases such as *we cannot accept a Muslim Europe, we must not allow ourselves to be subjugated, no to a Europe bent to Sharia!, full-face veil? no, thanks, or if you feel offended by the*

crucifix or the (Christmas) cradle, then this is not the place for you! show that rejection is presented as the defense of a cultural and moral order considered non-negotiable.

In these posts, the central element is not merely cultural or religious difference in itself, but its discursive representation as an illegitimate intrusion and imposition. This emerges particularly clearly in formulations such as *Islamic propaganda for the halal diet is more alive than ever. this too is a way of imposing their culture on ours. we cannot allow it or integration does not mean teaching Arabic in schools. we must not allow ourselves to be subjugated by those who are guests in our country.* In these cases, the Islamic presence is constructed as illegitimate insofar as it is interpreted as an attempt to redefine the cultural and symbolic boundaries of the community. It is precisely these judgments that establish exclusion as a discursively justified response.

6.2.1.3 Scenes and practices as objects of moral condemnation

The discourse is also structured through the moral evaluation of events or practices presented as shocking, disturbing, or unacceptable. Some posts construct moral condemnation through scenes considered unsettling, which acquire an emblematic value. For instance, the case in which *the MMA champion Khabib Nurmagomedov... did not shake the female host's hand during a live TV broadcast* is described as *an embarrassing scene that is indicative of the view of women in a certain Islamic world.* Similarly, *unacceptable images from some Muslim countries where it is common practice to see young girls wearing the Islamic veil or a long line of around a thousand men beating their chests and veiled women, separated by a black cloth... incredible scenes witnessed in Milan, not in Tehran* illustrate how moral condemnation is also constructed through references to practices perceived as incompatible and framed as needing to be brought to an end.

In these examples, the position of women functions as a key site of moral evaluation, through which broader judgments about Islam are articulated and criticised.

In addition, there are discourses surrounding practices described as abusive, improper, or fraudulent. When it is stated that *a system had been set up to exploit the good faith of donors and circumvent controls or enough abuse!* in reference to an illegal mosque, the discourse does not merely describe a problematic situation but reinterprets it as a moral violation of the social and legal order. Islam is thus associated not only with cultural incompatibility, but also with abuse, illegality, and deception.

6.2.1.4 Political critique as ethical denunciation

Another essential aspect concerns the link between moral judgment and political critique, particularly with regard to the left. In these segments, the left is not represented merely as a political opponent, but as a morally culpable actor, accused of complicity, submission, or betrayal. Expressions such as *a decision that, as usual, reeks of cultural submission on the part of the Democratic Party, unrestrained immigrationism promoted by the left and blessed by Brussels, a project endorsed by a complicit left that sells out our identity in exchange for votes, or the same left that applauds the release of the imam... identified as a threat to national security* clearly show that political conflict is moralised.

Within this framework, the left is constructed as an actor responsible not only for misguided political choices, but for deliberately exposing the community to danger and cultural transformation. Political critique thus takes the form of an ethical denunciation: it does not merely contest a political orientation but accuses a political camp of failing to protect—or even of actively undermining—collective identity, security, and values.

6.2.1.5 The security threat as a moral threat

Moral judgment is closely intertwined with the discursive construction of Islam as a security threat. Individuals or groups associated with Islam—most often, in these posts, imams—are described not only as dangerous, but as fundamentally incompatible with the national space and with the democratic order. Formulations such as *have you heard the harsh words of the imam of Bologna? we call for the immediate expulsion of this person from our nation, he preached an extremist Islam, contrary to European values, reports indeed indicate the presence of extremist imams and preachers throughout Italy who represent a threat to the security of our country, or a violent and committed preacher of radical Islam. their objective is crystal clear: sharia and the subversion of the democratic system* clearly show how the threat is constructed not only as a material risk, but as a danger to values, to the moral order, and to the continuity of the community.

For this reason, measures such as expulsion, the monitoring of mosques, the surveillance of imams, or the traceability of foreign funding are presented not merely as useful, but as morally justified. The link between security and morality is therefore particularly strong: the discourse tends to frame restrictions as an ethically necessary response to a threat that is simultaneously political, social, and value-based.

6.2.1.6 The positive legitimization of restrictive measures

A particularly interesting component of this discursive framework concerns the fact that moral judgment is expressed not only through condemnation, but also through the positive justification of restrictive measures. The statement *Lissone will be the first municipality in Italy to ban the burqa and the niqab... rightfully so, it is a matter of security and respect for women's rights* shows how the ban is constructed as an ethically grounded, rational, and necessary measure.

Similarly, proposals to place *mosques and Islamic centres* under surveillance, to track every euro of foreign funding, and to require that imams speak Italian are supported through formulations such as *I completely agree*, thereby transforming restriction into an expression of responsibility and moral approval. The same mechanism can be observed in statements such as *the Islamic veil represents not only a security issue but also an unacceptable instrument of oppression for women*, where the moral condemnation of the veil serves as the basis for justifying its prohibition.

In this sense, the discourse does not merely assert that something is wrong; it also constructs which actions are right, reasonable, and necessary.

6.2.1.7 The protection of women and children as ethical justification

Another key articulation concerns the use of the language of protection and safeguarding, particularly in relation to women and children. Segments such as *these young women must be saved from those who want to impose on them a life without freedom, the Islamic veil is a symbol of subjugation* show that Islam is often judged as a threat to vulnerable subjects—discursively represented by women and children—and that this very judgment allows restrictive policies and exclusionary positions to be reframed as ethical obligations.

Within this framework, references to foreign contexts play a crucial comparative role. Statements such as *we have expressed our solidarity with Iranian activists who are fighting for women's freedom* or *the courage of so many women who take to the streets and remove the Islamic veil is moving* construct a contrast between different socio-political contexts, reinforcing a dichotomy between freedom and

oppression. Through this comparison, Islam—particularly in its political dimension—is discursively positioned on the negative side of this opposition, especially in relation to the condition of women.

In this way, the protection of women and children is not a secondary theme, but a strategic component of the discourse, as it enables the transformation of opposition to Islam into a moral and humanitarian duty.

6.2.1.8 Indignation as an emotional amplifier

The emotional dimension of moral judgment is particularly evident in the use of indignation. Expressions such as *absurd, a disgrace! chilling, what a shame!!!, or the English silenced... a disgraceful double standard* do not necessarily add new information but instead amplify the existing condemnation. Indignation sharpens the evaluative stance, making it more immediate, more urgent, and more engaging, thereby increasing the persuasive force of the message and predisposing the audience to a prompt reaction.

6.2.2 Language and the Symbolic Construction of Islam

6.2.2.1 Terminological selection and the semantic reduction of Islam

In some posts, the discursive construction of Islam also takes place through a highly selective lexical repertoire. The terms employed in these posts do not describe Islam in its plurality but rather define its meaning by systematically associating it with radicalisation, control, violence, and systemic threat. In this way, a form of semantic reduction is produced: Islam is rarely invoked in general or complex terms, but instead through a limited set of highly connoted labels. More specifically, a stable discursive lexicon emerges around the term *Islam*, whereby the word itself is consistently embedded within a network of negatively charged associations that shape its meaning in advance.

Among these, *Sharia* occupies a central position. Expressions such as *to Sharia!*, *the use of Islamic Sharia*, or simply *Sharia* construct Islam as a normative system incompatible with Western values and as a condensed symbol of legal, cultural, and political threat. Here, *Sharia* does not appear as a concept to be explained or contextualised, but rather as a signal word that encapsulates the idea of incompatibility.

Equally significant is the reference to *radical Islam*, which directly associates Islam with radicalisation and danger. Formulations such as *dangers linked to radical Islam* or simply *of radical Islam* make visible a key discursive point: Islam is primarily conceived and named through the lens of radicalism. In the same direction, expressions such as *Islamic radicalisation* suggest an ongoing, dynamic, and expanding process.

This lexical field is further reinforced by terms such as *Islamic propaganda*, *Islamic caliphates*, *Islamic regime*, *Muslim Brotherhood*, and *taharrush gamea* (meaning “collective harassment” that refers to situations in which groups of men carry out coordinated or opportunistic sexual assaults in crowded public spaces, surrounding, isolating, and abusing women), which further specify the nature of the perceived threat. *Islamic propaganda* constructs Islam as an active strategy of dissemination and influence; *Islamic caliphates* evoke an alternative political order opposed to democracy; *Islamic regime* associates Islam with authoritarian forms of governance; reference to the *Muslim Brotherhood* personalises the threat in a concrete organisation; and *taharrush gamea* links Islam to practices of sexual violence and social deviance.

Even when the term *Islamophobia* appears, it does not open up space for reflection on discrimination but is instead inserted into a polemical logic that tends to delegitimise public debate on Islam as in rhetorical questions such as *Why does the European Union waste millions of euros in public funds on projects about Islam, Islamophobia, Sharia, and the Quran?* Overall, this terminological selection produces a powerful effect: it establishes an implicit equivalence between Islam, radicalism, coercion, and danger, thereby minimising the complexity of the phenomenon.

6.2.2.2 Metaphors as cognitive reorganisation of the phenomenon

The use of metaphors constitutes another crucial element in the discursive construction of Islam. In particular, the conceptual metaphor IMMIGRATION IS WAR emerges as among the most recurrent and structuring devices, underpinning expressions such as *to fight, to defend, battle, siege, surrender, we will defend it with all our strength, or I will not surrender* transform discourse on Islam into a narrative of war, in which the presence of an enemy, a battlefield, and a subject to be protected is implicitly presupposed.

Through these formulations, complex social phenomena such as immigration, religious pluralism, or integration are reinterpreted as forms of confrontation and conflict. Islam or *Islamisation* are constructed as active and aggressive forces, while Italy and Europe are discursively framed as territories under attack.

Alongside war metaphors, expansionary metaphors also emerge, such as *it spreads like wildfire*, as well as catastrophic metaphors, such as *Islamic nightmare*. In both cases, the discourse reinforces perceptions of pervasiveness, inevitability, and loss of control. Metaphors thus contribute to a cognitive reorganisation of reality, constructing Islam as an active, aggressive, expansive, and difficult-to-contain phenomenon.

6.2.2.3 Use of quantification

The discourse is further reinforced through quantification. (High) numbers (“aggregation”), quantities, and references to growth serve to make the threat more concrete, measurable, and seemingly objective. Expressions such as *Muslim students are already the majority, around a thousand people, the largest mosque in Europe, millions of euros, or increasingly numerous cases of churches converted into mosques* construct an image of continuous expansion and contribute to a strong sense of alarmism.

Here, the point is not merely the numerical information itself, but its discursive function: quantity becomes evidence of threat. The repetition of formulations such as *as yet nth abuse or yet nth incident* suggests that the phenomenon is recurrent, systemic, and increasing. Demographic growth, the multiplication of mosques, large-scale figures, and economic quantification all contribute to reinforcing the idea of an expanding process.

6.2.2.4 Negative lexicon

A further level concerns the strongly connoted vocabulary that accompanies the representation of Islam. Words such as *nightmare, serious threat, disgrace, terrifying, violent, anti-democratic and freedom-denying, death threats, or unauthorised mosque* construct a highly negative semantic environment within which Islam is perceived as alarming, degrading, and incompatible.

More specifically, the lexicon of danger reinforces the securitarian dimension; the lexicon of shame intensifies moral condemnation; the lexicon of hostility represents Islam as an active threat; while more generic yet strongly evaluative terms contribute to a semantic saturation of the phenomenon, making it difficult to conceptualise Islam outside the framework of threat.

6.2.3 Islam and the Construction of Threat

6.2.3.1 Migration, integration and citizenship: Islam as a social and political problem

Another important theme concerns the intersection between Islam and migration. The analysis shows that migration is one of the main discursive vehicles through which Islam is problematised. Immigration is not discursively represented as a structural phenomenon, but rather as a problem, often directly or implicitly associated with the Islamic presence. Expressions such as *unrestrained immigrationism*, *uncontrolled Islamic immigration*, or *we will continue to combat irregular immigration* demonstrate that Islam is frequently constructed through dynamics of entry and expansion.

Particularly relevant is the way in which the discourse addresses the issue of integration. Formulations such as *this is not how integration is achieved! this is anything but integration! those who truly integrate, stay*, or *this is not integration* clearly show that integration is not conceived as a reciprocal process, but rather as a unilateral adaptation to the values of the *us* (in-group). In this sense, Islam is constructed as either incapable of, or unwilling to, integrate, and integration becomes a moral criterion for inclusion or exclusion.

This dynamic extends to the issue of citizenship, which is represented as an undue concession and a risk to collective identity. Phrases such as *citizenship is not something handed out for free, he obtained citizenship... without speaking the language or giving away citizenship to foreigners* show that full national belonging is made conditional upon adherence to criteria unilaterally defined by the dominant group. Within this framework, Islam is constructed simultaneously as a migratory phenomenon, a social problem, and a political issue.

6.2.3.2 The geography of threat

The discourse makes the threat concrete and everyday by locating it within familiar spaces. Islam is not presented solely as an abstract or ideological phenomenon, but as a visible presence in schools, hospitals, streets, neighbourhoods, squares, shops, places of worship, and public spaces. Schools occupy a central position in this construction: expressions such as *Islamisation in schools*, *halal menus in schools*, *integration does not mean teaching Arabic in schools*, or *at school there is no limit to how bad things can get* transform sites of education and socialisation into key spaces of perceived threat. Hospitals, as in *in Italian hospitals there are increasingly frequent signs in Arabic*, indicate that the Islamic presence is made visible within public institutions, while neighbourhoods, streets, and squares—in *our neighbourhoods, on the streets, in Piazza Duomo in Milan*—render the threat proximate, every day, and tangible. In this way, Islam is not described as distant or exceptional, but as embedded in daily life: the threat becomes concrete rather than merely abstract.

At the same time, geographical references play a strategic role in reinforcing this construction. At the macro level, Italian cities such as Milan, Rome, Bologna, Naples, or Padua make the phenomenon appear close and recognisable, while places such as Molenbeek and Brussels function as emblematic examples of a supposedly completed Islamisation. References to extra-European contexts such as Tehran, Kabul, Saudi Arabia, or Damascus introduce an implicit contrast, suggesting that what is

associated with those contexts could also represent Europe's future. Formulations such as *not in Tehran, but in Milan* symbolically reduce the distance between *here* and *elsewhere*, contributing to the geographical mapping of threat across local, European, and global scales. Space, therefore, is not neutral, but is organised as evidence of transformation.

Within this framework, the discursive construction of Islam extends from the national to the European scale, where it is represented as a force capable of reshaping the very identity of the continent. Expressions such as *Europe is changing its face, the Islamisation of Europe is increasingly becoming a reality, the nightmare of an Islamised Europe... is just around the corner, or we cannot accept a Muslim Europe* clearly show that change is not interpreted as evolution or pluralisation, but as a process of replacement and distortion. This transformation is associated with a threat to European values, democracy, Christianity, and women's rights, as reflected in formulations such as *they want to rule us and transform our democratic countries into Islamic caliphates or Christian Europe, never Muslim*, which reinforce the idea of a systemic and antagonistic alternative.

Finally, a particularly significant element is the redefinition of the threat itself: danger is no longer located outside Europe, but within it, becoming an integral part of European social and geographical space.

6.2.3.3 Discursive actors: who threatens, who protects, who betrays

A central dynamic of the discourse is the construction of a clear opposition between a legitimate *we* and a problematic *them*. Islam is represented as an external or antagonistic force in relation to an already defined community. Expressions such as *we must fight against Islamisation... to defend our identity, our culture, our traditions, to impose their culture on ours, we must not allow ourselves to be subjugated by those who are guests in our country, or they want to rule us* clearly illustrate this opposition.

This opposition is also articulated through a precise selection of actors, which makes the phenomenon concrete and recognisable. On the one hand, a *we* is constructed, composed of Italians, Europeans, citizens, women to be protected, children, families, law enforcement and political actors, particularly from the right, who present themselves as defenders of identity and security. On the other hand, a *them* is constructed, composed of Muslims, imams, Islamists, migrants, foreigners, the left, and institutions perceived as complicit.

The *we* is associated with positive values such as identity, freedom, democracy and security, and is constructed as a community under threat, as reflected in expressions such as *masters in our own home! to erase our roots and our identity, or our children will grow up ignoring who they are and where they come from*. By contrast, the *they* is represented as the bearer of incompatible models, which impose, divide, and threaten society, as indicated by expressions such as *not all cultures are compatible with ours, Muslims are beginning to impose on us what we must watch, or young foreigners who hate us... and would like to impose Islamism on us*.

This opposition also defines the conditions of belonging. Phrases such as *those who truly integrate, stay... otherwise they go back to their own country, if you feel offended... this is not the place for you! or they do not deserve to stay in Italy!* Show that inclusion is made conditional upon adaptation to the *we*, while exclusion applies to those who do not conform to these criteria.

Finally, this dichotomy is not only descriptive but also mobilising. Expressions such as *it is time to choose which side to stand on, let us fight together for our country, or we will continue to combat irregular immigration and processes of Islamisation* transform the opposition into a call to action.

Overall, the discourse constructs *we* and *them* as morally opposed poles, defining boundaries of belonging, rendering Islam a concrete threat through specific actors, and legitimising the need for defence and intervention.

Within this framework, the left is represented as a promoter of immigration and multiculturalism, incapable of protecting the community and often complicit in Islamisation. Muslims are generalised as a homogeneous and threatening collective; the imam becomes a central figure of radicalisation; Muslim women appear simultaneously as visible symbols of Islamisation and as victims in need of protection; Muslim men are more frequently associated with traditionalism, radicalism, or violence. By contrast, the right—and in particular the Lega Nord—presents itself as a defensive and active actor, capable of taking concrete action.

It is important to note that this configuration of roles is also shaped by the nature of the empirical material: the posts analysed were published by the Lega Nord, which contributes to the prominence of a self-representation centred on protection, security, and political agency.

This system of actors organises the discourse as a network of opposing roles: those who threaten, those who are threatened, those who betray, and those who defend.

6.2.3.4 Gender, oppression and value Incompatibility

A final key dimension concerns the construction of Islam through gendered power relations. The discourse interprets the relationship between Islam and women as a condensed proof of the phenomenon's incompatibility with Western values. Expressions such as *a vision of women as submissive, they must be submissive and beaten, veiled women separated by a cloth, girls forced into arranged marriages, or the Islamic veil... an instrument of oppression* clearly show that Muslim women become one of the primary symbolic sites through which the definition of threat is articulated. The control of the female body, spatial segregation, marital coercion, arranged marriage and violence are represented as evidence of the patriarchal, hierarchical and oppressive nature of Islam. In this way, the issue of gender functions as a bridge between cultural critique, securitisation, and the legitimation of exclusion.

6.2.3.5 From threat construction to political action

The discursive representation of Islam in the analysed posts does not merely describe a cultural, social, or security threat, but is consistently oriented toward specific political objectives. Islam is constructed as a phenomenon that requires a clear, normative, and operational response: the discourse does not simply state what Islam is but also defines what should be done in response to it. The proposed measures are presented not as mere political options, but as necessary, reasonable, and morally justified.

A first central topic concerns the defense of Western and national values, understood in terms of identity, culture, traditions and freedom. Expressions such as *let us defend our civilisation, our values, our freedom, we must defend our traditions, our culture, our identity, we will defend our history, our roots, and our rights with all our strength, or let us defend Italy, our culture, our security* show how opposition to Islam is constructed as a cultural and patriotic duty. This identity-based frame is also

translated into concrete demands, such as requiring imams to *speak Italian and preach in accordance with the Constitution* or calling for *total transparency on foreign funding*.

A second relevant dimension concerns the Islamic veil, which is not treated as a simple expression of religious practice, but as a direct object of political intervention. Formulations such as *to ban the burqa and the niqab, to ban it for girls and adolescents in schools, “Lega” campaign against the Islamic veil, ban on full-face veils in public places, or to ban the burqa in schools and public buildings* show how the veil is constructed both as a symbol of oppression and as a regulatory issue, to be addressed through bans and sanctions.

A further dimension concerns the control of religious space, particularly mosques and Islamic centres, which are represented as problematic sites requiring intervention. Expressions such as *mosques and Islamic centres under control: every structure must be registered, authorised and subject to constant checks, together with citizens against the large mosque in Sassuolo, the Islamic centre has been closed, or the unauthorised mosque that we managed to shut down* show how religious presence is reframed as an issue of public order and urban governance. At the same time, security emerges as a primary objective, through formulations such as *for the safety of our children and the future of Italy or committed to security*, which directly link the representation of Islam as a threat to the need for preventive and control measures.

Another relevant element concerns the protection of women, which is used to justify specific political proposals. For instance, the statement *the “Lega” proposes the crime of Islamic harassment, a strong signal to combat aberrant practices such as taharrush gamea* (meaning “collective harassment” that refers to situations in which groups of men carry out coordinated or opportunistic sexual assaults in crowded public spaces, surrounding, isolating, and abusing women), shows how the protection of women is mobilised to legitimise normative interventions, constructing political action as a form of protection and liberation.

Finally, some formulations synthesise the overall direction of the discourse, such as *we will continue to combat irregular immigration and the processes of Islamisation of Italy and Europe*, highlighting a broader project in which security, identity, control and opposition to Islamisation converge into a coherent strategy.

Overall, the discourse does not merely represent Islam as a problem, but constructs a structured set of political responses, presented as necessary to defend the community, its values, and the social order.

6.2.4 Conclusion

Overall, the thematic analysis shows that the discursive construction of Islam in the examined posts is not merely descriptive but constitutes a strategic process through which meanings, moral hierarchies, and political orientations are produced. Islam is systematically framed as culturally incompatible, securitarily dangerous, and socially problematic through a combination of moral judgments, selective lexical choices, metaphors, quantification, and spatial representations that reinforce its perception as a widespread and growing threat. This construction is further consolidated through the opposition between a legitimate “we” and an incompatible “them”, as well as through the selection of actors, places, and practices that render the threat concrete, everyday, and visible.

At the same time, the discourse does not merely define the problem, but explicitly directs attention toward political and moral responses, presented as necessary and legitimate. The defense of identity,

security, and rights, particularly women’s rights, functions as the main justificatory framework for exclusionary positions and restrictive measures. In this sense, the emotional dimension, and indignation in particular, plays a crucial role in reinforcing the persuasive force of the message, while the specific communicative dynamics of Instagram, such as hooks and call-to-action strategies, contribute to transforming the discourse into a device of mobilisation capable of actively engaging the audience. These elements show that the political discourse analysed does not merely reflect reality, but actively participates in its symbolic construction, producing a vision of Islam as a multidimensional threat and contributing to the legitimation of specific practices of exclusion, control, and political intervention. On this basis, the following section offers a more in-depth linguistic analysis.

6.3 Results of the Rhetorical-Linguistic Analysis of Markers of Populist Discourse

The posts display most, though not all, and not to the same extent, of the typical features of populist discourse identified in the literature (Mudde, 2000; Moffitt & Tormey, 2014; Engesser et al., 2017; Moffitt, 2022). Central among these is what may be termed a “triangulation” between one in-group (“we”, “the people”) and two out-groups: on the one hand, (parts of) the elite, reflecting “antagonism on the vertical level,” and, on the other, a population-internal minority, reflecting “antagonism on the horizontal level” (Rothut et al., 2025, p. 55).

The discourse further evokes a sense of crisis and urgency—what has been described as “fast politics”—with the elite positioned as the source of the crisis (Moffitt & Tormey, 2013). It includes appeals to “the people” and constructs their representation through a leader figure (Laclau, 2005). At the same time, it frames heritage, values, and rights as being under threat and relies on performative elements (Moffitt & Tormey, 2013; Moffitt, 2022).

While features such as sustained social media presence, livestreaming and on-site reporting are less prominent, the discourse exhibits a tabloid style characterised by transgressive language and behaviour, flamboyance and political incorrectness. We now turn to the concrete linguistic markers and rhetorical strategies that underpin these features.

6.3.1 Actor triangulation

The **in-group** is constructed as the Italian people (of non-left leaning) together with the right-wing politicians (leader figures²) making their case, and some single local authorities. Occasionally, actors such as children in Gaza, Iranian citizens (as oppressed by their government), and, at times, Muslim women and children are associated with the in-group. These are referred to as *ad hoc* in-group members in what follows. The core in-group (the Italian people of non-left leaning) is not only appealed to, but it is also intensively encouraged to interact with the right-wing agenda, however mostly online and remarkably little offline (see below in section performativity, exhortations 6.3.5). Direct interaction of the online in-group spokespersons (the authors of the Instagram posts) with the two out-groups is limited.

The **vertical outgroup** is represented as “the Left”, the EU/Europe/Bruxelles, some local councils, some local school administrators (in Italy, Belgium and Austria), and some other authorities like municipalities. Belgium, and to a lesser extent Austria, are depicted as *nightmare future scenarios* (Ross & Rivers, 2017) that could become a reality in Italy without preventive action.

² Due to the source and format of the data, the populist concept of leader figure emerges only indirectly as the authors of the Instagram posts.

The **horizontal outgroup** is represented by Muslim migrants (in Italy, Belgium, Austria) as well as “terrorists” (Hamas, or generalised), as well as “Islam(isaton)” in a kind of personified version. The Iranian Government also represents an out-group. We mention it here in association to other Muslim actors, because – although it is a “vertical (~ elite)” institution – its discursively constructed role as a direct threat is closer to that constructed for the Muslim group than to the one constructed for the Italian and European “Left” elite, which is more the naïve or political correct facilitator of the threat (see below).

One of the most important rhetorical tools for framing the actors of the triangular constellation in our data is “transitivity”, the discursive representation of people “in regard to what they are doing”, a subtle way of shaping other people’s perceptions of the described actors (Machin & Mayr, 2025, chapter 6, p. 2).

In our transitivity analysis for our three actor groups, we follow Halliday’s (1994) categories of process types: *material* (doing concrete actions), *mental* (cognitive, affective, perceptive: can create empathy, but can also frame passivity), *verbal* (verbs of saying: having a voice = having power, sometimes too much power), *relational* (*be, have*: allow to present opinions as facts), and *existential* (*exist, happen*: together with nominalisations of actions, agency and responsibility can be obscured). (Machin & Mayr, 2025, chapter 6, p. 4-9)

The **in-group** or their representatives are presented as actively engaged (as grammatical subjects) in the following material processes: *abolish arranged marriages, dismantle the mosque, close down the Islamic centre, expel the imam, block the illegal mosque, forbid the burqa*. An ad hoc in-group members *expose/unveil the Islamic regime in few minutes* [a female Iranian activist and her testimony] or *challenge the Islamist regime* [Iranian women].

It further engages in verbal actions: *demand³ the immediate expulsion of the imam, propose the prohibition of the veil, and express solidarity with the Iranian people*. A mental process engaged with is: *regard fundamental⁴ (now more than ever)* – what the sender of the posts regards as ‘fundamental’ is the (continuous) taking of a series of actions that are: *support Matteo Salvini* (right-wing leader figure) *and strengthen the identity of The Lega* (right-wing party). The identity of the Lega is framed through the relational process of being: *close to the territories* [local anchorage], *applied to security, in the fight against decline, in the restitution of outer districts, and the support of law enforcement*.⁵ Another mental process⁶ is *not accept⁷*, when a municipality seeks to introduce the halal diet in its schools.

Some *ad hoc* or loosely associated members of the in-group are presented in passive constructions, as suffering under the horizontal out-group: like *subjugated* [Muslim] *women* (with the action as a resultative passive adjective), or [men and women in Iran] *are massacred by the Islamic regime* (with the agent present in adverbial form). The presented merits of in-group actors are hence dismantling

³ Boulomaic modality and directive speech act.

⁴ Strong deontic modality.

⁵ *Security, fight, decline, restitution, and support* are nouns that cover over verbal actions that are, by their nominalization, rendered less concrete, and hence requiring less commitment: it is not clear who has secured/will secure what, who has fought/will fight the decline (of what?) and when (“Nominalisation typically replaces verb processes with a noun construction, which can obscure agency and responsibility for an action, what exactly happened and when”, Machin/Mayr 2025, chap. 7, p. 1).

⁶ The reading of the original Italian formulation can also touch upon ‘not participate’, hence covering a less mental and more material process.

⁷ Boulomaic modality.

Islamic institutions or preventing their coming into being, being active in the political game, as well as publicly speaking up for their agenda.

The **vertically antagonised out-group** is presented as taking the following material actions: *close school for Ramadan, remove the cross from classrooms, introduce/make obligatory a halal menu in schools, sell out “our” identity, authorise the use of the Sharia, waste millions of Euros*. A group of material actions ((vividly) metaphoric, actually, but Machin and Mayr (2025) do not distinguish between such actions’ literal and metaphoric meaning) is the one describing this group’s deferring to the horizontal outgroup: *bend before Islamic integralism, bend before Sharia, [ready to] embrace Sharia and tread on democracy*.

A mental process is *want*⁸ *to donate citizenship to foreigners*, encompassing an intention to perform a material action. A relational process is: *be ready to* [embrace sharia and to tread on democracy], again comprising an intention to perform material actions. This out-group is, however, also portrayed as passive objects of material actions: *gagged* (‘not daring to speak up’), *humiliated by the citizens* (in local elections).

This group is hence framed as guilty of accommodating (or intending to accommodate) Islamic lifestyle, as weak, and as rightfully punished for that.

The **horizontally antagonised out-group** is presented as the one most active of all actor groups, having the (by far) longest list of verbal processes tied to it.

It is presented as taking the following material actions: *not accept handshakes, go to pray at the (Christian) sanctuary, get organised to create a real Islamic national party, bring [daycare] children to the mosque and have them knee towards Mecca, bring a class to the mosque, make them knee before the imam and proudly publish the picture on the school’s intranet, direct monetary donations towards Hamas, force girls into arranged marriages, try*⁹ *to impose its rules and customs* [Islam as personified actor], *block out any reference to our culture, impose us what we should watch, how we should dress and what we should believe in, wipe out our culture, wipe out our roots, rewrite our civilisation, force to wear the veil by violence or threats, encircle and abuse women in groups, subjugate and beat women, arrive and kill Christians* [in Damascus], *force a baker to longer sell ham in his quiches, separate women* [from men during public religious celebrations]. The veil is defined as an *instrument of oppression* (again a nominalisation of a verb). Other nominalisations are found: *the subjugation of women and the subversion of the state* [by an Islamic party defined as *bearer of anti-democratic and liberticide values*; the values are qualified by adjectives in themselves antagonistic and even associated to material action ‘killing liberty’]. A particular subgroup of material action described as tied to the horizontal out-group, namely the evocation of the rapid and far-reaching change it creates, again emphasising urgency: *expands like a pool of oil* [Islamisation], *is spreading in our neighborhoods under [our] very eyes* [Islam], *is happening at full speed* [the substitution (nominalisation) of our culture]. The expressions follow a pattern of combining verbs in the present tense, also in the continuous form, suggesting “ongoingness”, together with vivid adverbials (*like a pool of oil, at full speed, under our very eyes*) that further support the impression of the events’ magnitude and impact.

These material processes cover pursuing the imposing of Islamic lifestyle, customs, and rules, as well as going against or even blocking out Western culture, rules and identity, all presented as happening with assiduity, rapidly, and on a large scale. The high activity level of the horizontal out-group evoked

⁸ Boulomaic modality.

⁹ Boulomaic modality.

by the large amount of dynamic processes attributed to it is another factor in the creation of a sense of urgency.

Cognitive processes attributed to the horizontal out-group are as follows: *hate us, our way of life, women and want¹⁰ to impose Islamism; want to rule us and transform our democratic countries into Islamic caliphates*, expressing goal-orientation.

Even if out-groups very often are not given a voice (or power) by being attributed verbal processes, sometimes, attributing verbal processes to them can be performed so as to suggest that an actor has too much power (Machin & Mayr, 2025: chapter 6, p. 9). This is very probably the case for the following verbal actions attributed to the horizontal outgroup: *demand¹¹ application of Islamic law, demand to send the daughter to school with the complete veil (burqa), preach hate, saying unacceptable¹² phrases, say as the first thing [in office] “you don’t like the veil?”, say “if you do not like women with veils and Islamism, go and live in other parts of Belgium”*. Indirect verbal processes are expressed by the formulation *active propaganda*, with the adjective *active* emphasising systematicity. *Propaganda* in itself comprises the verbal action’s intentional component to expand an ideology. These contexts evoke (too) much “voice”/power of the horizontal outgroup.

We want to round off the transitivity analysis with a short note on the usage of modal verbs tied to the three actor groups: deontic *must*, deontic *can*, and boulomaic *want* (also already treated above as a mental process).

The in-group, by the attributed modal verbs, is firmly anchored in the deontic realm. There it is either bound by duties they owe themselves: *must fight against the Islamisation of our cities, must defend our traditions, must raise our voice*, or denying permission to the outgroup to impose their agenda on them: *cannot have ourselves succumbed by who is guest in our country, cannot remain silent while somebody rewrites our civilisation*. Some contexts of *must* (own duty; negated: prohibition) with reference to phenomena talked about: *Italy must be defended*; [unacceptable¹³ and dramatic violence] *must make us think deeper*; [to be sent away from the neighborhood by the horizontal out-group] *must not happen her*. Finally, there are deontic expectations attributed to the out-group regarding what the in-group (according to the out-group) should do: *must watch, must wear, must believe determinate things; must give up*. A hyperbolic and metaphoric phrasing is *you* [second-person plural] *must put me underground before I wear a veil*. One example is a boulomaic

want, but its realisation is denied: *this is not the Europe that we want*. The choice of modal verbs mirrors a scenario of the in-group being bound by outer necessities, not by their own will.

The vertical outgroup (the Left) has one boulomaic *want* attributed to them: *want to use ius scholae for regulating citizenship*. It is actively and intentionally working with a plan.

The same is true for the horizontal out-group. They are often tied to boulomaic *want*: *want to rule us and transform our democratic countries into islamic califats, want to convince us that Europe has Islamic roots, [can do what] they want, want to impose Islam on us, want to impose Islamism on us, want to bring a certain vision of the woman to Europe, want the Islamisation of schools*. Boulomaic modality is also expressed by *dream*: *his dream: Ramadan as a national holiday!; the Islamists’ dream*:

¹⁰ Boulomaic modality.

¹¹ ijective speech act

¹² Undesirability (appreciative modality) as well as blameworthiness (axiological modality), according to the speaker’s set of norms.

¹³ Undesirability (appreciative modality) as well as blameworthiness (axiological modality), according to the speaker’s set of norms.

subjugate us as infidels. Further, the noun *willingness* (with the same lexical root as *want*) is tied to an absence: *have no willingness to integrate*. Then, a series of deontic *can* marks space for unbound liberty: *can do* [what they want], *can close an institute for Ramadan*, *can initiate projects to teach Islam to children*.

Both out-groups are hence portrayed as making plans and act freely according to those plans, while the in-group is presented as not having freedom of agency in this social situation. There is furthermore a compelling modal relation between the two outgroups: the “enabling” vertical out-group (the left elite) and the “enabled” horizontal out-group (Muslim immigrants). The roles of these two groups are tied together by a certain kind of deontic modality¹⁴, namely in its version of *permission* expressed by the modal verb *can*. It is the left elite that *permits* Muslim immigrants to promote their customs and rules.

The appeal to the people is created by actor triangulation where the people are instantiated as part of the in-group whose interests should be defended, as well as by the populations’ (potential and encouraged) active involvement in online communication with political actors (see section 6.3.5 on performativity below).

6.3.2 The evocation of crisis and urgency

Besides the scenes used as hooks in many Instagram posts that are supposed to present themselves as outrageous for the in-group, together with the actions and statements of the horizontal out-group (see above), there is a series of other rhetorical-linguistic strategies deployed in the data that evoke crisis and urgency. These other phenomena are exclamations (as marked in the data by exclamation marks) and appeal to emotions, as well as “aggregation” (the use of high numerical values tied to actors thereby treated as “statistics”, Machin & Mayr, 2015, chapter 6, p. 18).

Very often, exclamations also contain modal nuances and appeals to emotions, which we will mark when mentioning the respective examples.

The exclamations in our data have various forms according to a) syntax and b) speech act: a) they can be in the form of whole sentences (utterances containing a finite verb) or utterances without finite verbs (syntactic phrases: *absurd!*, *an unacceptable situation!*), and b) they can be assertive, directive or in the form of informative questions.

Whole, assertive exclamative sentences are: *The Lega continues to oppose to that!*; *the Lega opposes to that!*; *Yes, I am guilty of all that!* [referring to own political activity]; *the Islamic centre has been shut down!*; *in a bit, I’ll be in front of the illegal mosque that we managed to shut down!*; [person X,] *you came a long way!* [ironic]; *This is not going to happen!* [a form of “prophecy”]; *this is not valued Italian sport but only a sell-out!* [Supercup in Saudi Arabia with veiled women and names in Arabic on the shirts of the Italian team]; *they don’t deserve to be in Italy!*; *This is absurd!* [blameworthy: axiological modality in *absurd*]; *Sharia is incompatible with our values!* [blameworthy: axiological modality in *incompatible*]; *if you feel offended by the cross and the [Christmas] cradle, well, then it’s not here you should live!* [in combination with a conditional clause, (weak) deontic modality in *should*: (weak) prescription]; *I continue my fight against submission!*; *Islamisation is more and more a threat!*

There is one example with a directive whole sentence in the second person singular: *Mayor, shut down the mosque!*

¹⁴ Deontic modality.

Exclamations in the form of noun phrases are: *An unacceptable situation!* [blameworthy: axiological modality in *unacceptable*]; *What a shame* [= shameful situation!] [blameworthy: axiological modality in *shame*]; [we won't have it:] *Masters in our own house!*

There is one exclamation in the form of an adjectival phrase: *absurd!* [blameworthy: axiological modality in *absurd*], and one in the form of a prepositional phrase: *In Europe?!?!* [which is also a rhetorical question¹⁵].

There are also verbless exclamations typical for political slogans based on the templates *enough with* and *no to*: *enough with cultural submission!*; *enough with Islamisation!*; *enough with abuse!*; *no to choices that become submission!*; *no to a Europe bending down to Sharia! No to the Islamisation of our cities!*; *no to harmful choices and decisions that clearly signal submission to Islam!*

These slogans express blameful situations and are hence instantiations of axiological modality.

There is also one example of direct address to the out-group in the form of a directive: *Go away! Out!* [combining an imperative with a direction adverbial, both with outward-moving deixis]. Besides expressing urgency, this instance also expresses direct confrontation with the out-group, who is usually talked about (in the third person), but not talked to or with (in the second person).

The exclamations in the data combine hence an evocation of urgency together with modalities of blaming and prescribing.

Another way of evoking urgency and a sense of crisis is by the appeal to (negative) emotions. This can be done in three ways: content with emotion-activating potential (e.g. creating outrage or fear), emotionally loaded vocabulary (*dramatic*, *incredible*, *extraordinary*), or explicit mentioning of emotions (*horrible*, *fear*) (Gabbai-Müller/Kratschmer 2025: 139).

We analysed content designed to create fear and outrage in our above section on thematic analysis as well as the functioning of hooks in short-form online messaging (see above p.17).

Also, in our presentation of transitivity patterns as well as exclamations, we already pointed to vocabulary with axiological modality (expressing blamefulness), which also contains a potential of creating repulsion, outrage, or fear.

Examples of mentioned emotions are the following: *chilling* [about the words of an imam on the role of the woman in Islam and Sharia], *hate us, preach hate*; *we are weary of people wanting to impose rules going against our values*; *you don't make me afraid!*

Examples for emotionally loaded adjectives are *incredible scenes*, *dramatic violence*.

Finally, urgency can also be created by "aggregation", the use of high numerical values tied to actors thereby treated as "statistics", and not as people (Machin/Mayr 2015, ch. 6, p. 18). Also, high numbers can create a spurious impression of objectivity (Van Dijk 1991).

The following examples of aggregation are found in our data: *more and more numerous cases of churches converted to mosques*; *thousands of people*; *a long line of thousands of people* [the last two referring to Islamic celebrations in public space]; *the nth abuse of multiculturalist ideology*; *the nth case of a girl forced into an arranged marriage*; *about millions [sic] of Euro* [in donations redirected to Hamas].

These numbers frame immigration as a substantial as well as costly problem.

¹⁵ See more on questions in p.35 below.

6.3.3 Performativity

Performativity in Moffit's sense of staging political activity is documented in our data by the very use of Instagram as a communications platform, with its affordances of photographic and video content, live streaming, and audience involvement. By exploiting the communicative conventions of short-form messaging, like the use of hooks with emotional appeal and the staging of an unnuanced actor triangulation with what seems a deliberate infraction of political correctness, this form of communication can be categorised as tabloid style (Moffit & Tourmey, 2013). While the presentation of the content is in no way neutral or objective, vulgar language could not be documented.

The focus seems to lie in audience involvement. Appeal to the people and in-group cohesion is aimed at by mobilisation of the single political actor's online audience by so-called *calls to action* in the form of questions to be answered in the comment section and exhortations (directive speech acts) to participate actively on the platform and (more rarely) offline.

Our data contain different types of questions: genuine information-seeking questions, rhetorical questions, as well as questions where it is unclear whether they are genuine or rhetorical. The genuine questions are the fewest, which seems surprising, since it goes against the platform logic of making the audience answer in the comment section: *and you, what do you think?*

Again surprisingly, the biggest group is the rhetorical questions, which do not directly invite an answer, but could still have, due to their built-in provocativeness, an effect stimulating a reaction: *Where are the demonstrations of the Left when men and women in Iran get massacred by the Islamic regime?; You get [understand] that?; Are we aware of where we are heading?; Why does Europe not start to defend our identity, our traditions our culture instead?; and tomorrow?; in Europe?!?! [also an exclamation, see above]; why does the European Union waste millions of euros of public funds on projects on Islam, on Islamophobia, on Sharia, on the Koran?*

It is unclear whether a series of questions are rhetorical or genuine, a possible deliberate strategy to prompt reflection among those unsure of the answer and provoke reactions from those who believe they know it: *have you heard the harsh words of the imam?; If this can happen in Belgium, what prevents this from happening also here?; Do you remember the guy who used an ambulance as a taxi?*

While questions do not appear to be fully exploited in this dataset, possibly because simple requests for opinions or conversation tend to generate lower engagement online (Chae, 2021), exhortations are used more actively. There are exhortations in the form of a second person plural imperative for the verbs *look* (two instances) and the verb *hear* (eight instances), both referring to the visual or auditory content of the hook. One instance of the verb *tune in* encourages to follow an upcoming live stream. Three instances of the particle *ecco*, a non-verbal particle exhorting to witness visually or auditorily also refers to the content of the hook. All these exhortations are confined to agency on the online platform.

There are only two direct exhortations to perform actions offline: *Mayor, shut down the mosque* [imperative second person singular, also mentioned under exclamations, see above]; *Let's defend Italy* [imperative inclusive first-person plural].

There are also instances that could be categorised as indirect exhortations by a range of different linguistic markers: *we must react* [with the deontic verb *must* (strong obligation) in the inclusive first person plural]; *It's time to choose on which side to be* [focusing on the urgency of the action]; *Stop to excursions to the mosque* [*stop* is not a verb in Italian, it function more like *no to*]; *Enough with initiatives that Islamise schools* [without exclamation mark, but all exclamations with *enough with*, see

above, can also be counted in this group of indirect exhortations, which is also true for all the contexts with *no to above*]; *No more closings for Ramadan*.

Direct exhortations are hence mostly about witnessing what was posted or getting connected for live-streaming, hence limited to the online sphere. The two direct exhortations with offline reference are addressed either to a specific individual (a mayor) or to a collective “we.” The latter, along with all indirect exhortations, is marked by considerable vagueness regarding both the intended actor and the concrete action. As a result, there is no evidence of attempts to mobilise specific actors toward concrete, potentially harmful offline actions.

6.3.4 Conclusion

Our *transitivity* analysis has shown that in-group actors are presented as meritorious through dismantling Islamic institutions or preventing their coming into being, being active in the political game, as well as publicly speaking up for their agenda. The vertical out-group is framed as guilty of accommodating (or intending to accommodate) Islamic lifestyle, as weak, and as rightfully punished for that. The horizontal out-group is portrayed with a high activity level imposing of Islamic lifestyle, customs and rules, as well as going against or even blocking out Western culture, rules and identity, all presented as happening with assiduity, rapidly and on a large scale, which also creates a sense of urgency. Contexts depicting verbal processes evoke (too) much “voice”/power of the horizontal outgroup.

The choice of *modal verbs* tied to the in-group mirrors a scenario where they are bound by outer necessities, not by their own will. Both out-groups are portrayed as making plans and acting freely according to those plans, while the in-group is presented as not having freedom of agency in this social situation. It is the left elite that *permits* Muslim immigrants to promote their customs and rules.

The *exclamations* in the data combine an evocation of urgency together with *modalities* of blaming and prescribing. Urgency and the sense of crisis are also evoked by the appeal to (negative) *emotions* by (e.g., outrageous) content, by emotionally loaded vocabulary as well as by vocabulary denoting emotions. The modality of blamefulness in general is tied to the two out-groups throughout the data.

The use of aggregation, whereby actors are associated with high numerical figures, frames immigration as both a substantial and a costly problem, reinforcing perceptions of scale, pressure and socio-economic burden.

While *questions* (genuine, rhetorical as well as cases unclear between the two) to platform users do not seem to be exploited to their full potential in this dataset, *exhortations* seem to be more actively used. Direct exhortations are mostly referring to witnessing what was posted or getting connected for live-streaming, hence limited to the online sphere. Indirect exhortations are characterised by a noteworthy vagueness, both regarding the intended actor and the concrete action, so no evidence for attempts to instigate concrete actors to concrete potentially harmful actions in the offline world could be found in the data.

7. Overview of Key Findings

These discursive patterns can be linked to broader processes of polarisation and normalisation.

First, the continuous construction of a contrast between in-group and out-group contributes to the polarisation of discourse, as the two groups are represented in opposing and non-equivalent ways. Linguistic markers reinforce this polarisation by distributing agency asymmetrically between groups. In particular, the in-group is often portrayed as having limited possibilities for action and as a defender

of values, identity, and traditions, while out-groups are described as dangerous and intentional, contributing to a polarised representation of social relations.

Second, these patterns also contribute to processes of normalisation. The recurrent use of references to scale, space, and urgency frames Islam as an intrinsic and persistent problem. Through repetition, such representations become naturalised, leading to their perception as factual and self-evident. Over time, these framings risk becoming stabilised as shared and uncontested interpretations, thereby reinforcing both the normalisation of exclusionary narratives and the persistence of polarised discourse.

8. Recommendations

Building on the findings of this report, several targeted recommendations can be formulated for different stakeholders involved in the production, regulation and interpretation of online discourse.

For **media practitioners**, including journalists, content creators and platform moderators, there is a need to avoid the uncritical amplification of alarmist and polarising framings, such as the recurrent use of threat metaphors, aggregation strategies and moralising narratives. Instead, greater emphasis should be placed on contextualisation, ensuring that references to Islam and migration are situated within broader socio-political realities and not reduced to simplified or stereotypical representations. In addition, the development of counter-narrative strategies that foreground complexity, plurality, and everyday coexistence is essential, alongside moderation practices that take into account not only explicit hate speech but also more subtle discursive patterns of othering and moralisation.

For **policymakers and regulators** at both national and European levels, the findings highlight the importance of moving beyond a narrow focus on illegal or harmful content toward addressing the underlying communicative structures that sustain polarisation. This includes fostering greater transparency regarding platform dynamics, particularly the role of engagement-driven features such as hooks and calls to action in amplifying emotionally charged and divisive content. There is also a need to promote clearer standards of accountability for political communication online, especially in relation to the representation of minority groups, and to support the development of interdisciplinary monitoring frameworks that combine computational and qualitative approaches to detect and assess emerging discursive risks.

For **educators and civil society actors**, the results underline the importance of strengthening critical media and discourse literacy. This involves equipping audiences not only with fact-checking skills but also with the ability to recognise rhetorical and linguistic strategies such as metaphor, aggregation and in-group/out-group constructions. Particular attention should be paid to platform-specific dynamics, including how Instagram-based communication strategies shape attention and engagement, as well as to the needs of more vulnerable audiences who may be disproportionately exposed to or affected by polarising content.

Finally, for **researchers and tool developers**, the study points to the value of advancing mixed-method approaches that integrate computational techniques with qualitative discourse analysis to capture both the scale and the nuance of online communication. Future work should further refine detection tools by incorporating linguistic and rhetorical markers and address existing conceptual gaps by more clearly distinguishing anti-Muslim discourse within broader migration-related narratives.

Overall, the findings suggest that the challenge of harmful and polarising discourse lies not only in individual pieces of content, but in the communicative structures through which meaning, urgency and threat are produced and circulated. Addressing these challenges therefore requires a shift from a sole focus on content moderation toward a more comprehensive, communication-sensitive approach to governance, practice and research.

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11. Appendices

A. Appendix 1

Table 1 number of posts per user

	n_posts	count
0	Francesco Emilio Borrelli	15191
1	Fratelli d'Italia	3563
2	Silvia Sardone	3228
3	Stefano Bonaccini	2778
4	Lega Nord	2596
5	Carlo Fidanza	2134
6	Isabella Tovaglieri	1628
7	Alleanza Verdi e Sinistra	1574
8	MoVimento 5 Stelle	1464
9	Paolo Borchia	1422
10	Forza Italia	1395
11	Anna Cisint	1389
12	Susanna Ceccardi	1270
13	Brando Benifei	1147
14	Marco Squarta	977
15	Partito Democratico	960
16	Michele Picaro	886
17	Gaetano Pedulla	875
18	Matteo Ricci	865
19	Stefano Cavedagna	834
20	Francesco Torselli	785
21	Carolina Morace	778
22	Alessandro Zan	769

23	Roberto Vannacci	741
24	Valentina Palmisano	714
25	Dario Nardella	695
26	Nicola Procaccini	687
27	Letizia Moratti	686
28	Pasquale Tridico	669
29	Giuseppe Antoci	647
30	Sandro Ruotolo	538
31	Dario Tamburrano	522
32	Danilo Della Valle	517
33	Aldo Patriciello	482
34	Nicola Zingaretti	479
35	Chiara Gemma	469
36	Daniele Polato	460
37	Antonio Decaro	446
38	Pina Picierno	445
39	Alessandra Moretti	439
40	Elisabetta Gualmini	434
41	Annalisa Corrado	414
42	Pierfrancesco Maran	411
43	Mario Furore	377
44	Cristina Guarda	366
45	Carlo Ciccio	343
46	Giorgio Gori	328
47	Ignazio Marino	298
48	Fulvio Martusciello	289

49	Benedetta Scuderi	240
50	Ilaria Salis	225
51	Salvatore De Meo	186
52	Massimiliano Salini	185
53	Mimmo Lucano	182
54	Giusi Princi	169
55	Giovanni Mori	144
56	Leoluca Orlando	128

B. Appendix 2

Table 2 presents the subset of topics identified as directly related to Islam

Topic ID	Topic Label	Posts (n)	BERTopic Representation (c-TF-IDF)	MMR Keywords	KeyBERT Keywords
65	Monfalcone Cisint and anti-Islam mobilisation	170	monfalcone, cisint, lega, anna, fincantieri	islamici, radicalizzazione, sindaco monfalcone	cisint monfalcone, lega monfalcone, comune monfalcone
94	Ramadan in schools and Islamisation panic	117	ramadan, scuola, pioltello,	chiudere scuola ramadan, stop islamizzazione	islamizzazione scuole, scuola chiusa ramadan

			islamizzazione, moschea		
101	Women, feminism, and Islamic patriarchy claims	111	femministe, donne, velo, musulmane, sottomesse	silenzio femministe, patriarcato islamico	donne sottomesse, donne velo islamico
102	Veil bans and veil-as-oppression discourse	111	velo, velo islamico, sottomissione, integrale, bambine	divieto velo islamico, simbolo oppressione	velo islamico scuole, donna velo islamico
153	Iran and Afghanistan: women under Islamist regimes	75	iran, regime, donne, repressione, diritti	diritti donne, talebani, resistenza iraniana	donne afgane, ritiro dallafghanistan
159	Mosques, imams, and Muslim Brotherhood infiltration	72	moschea, musulmani, imam, fratelli musulmani, sharia	moschea abusiva, partito islamico	ghetto islamico, comunita islamiche
202	Reporting and shutting "irregular" mosques	56	moschea, lega, padova, centri islamici, moschee	mappare centri islamici, moschee irregolari	segnalazioni moschee irregolari, moschea irregolare
213	Islamist attacks and asylum-seeker securitisation	52	germania, monaco, attentato, islamista, terrorismo	terrorismo islamico, richiedente asilo	attentato avvenuto, monaco baviera
222	Lega TV messaging on Islamic radicalisation	50	radicalizzazione, lega, islamica, identita	battaglia radicalizzazione islamica	radicalizzazione lega, lotta radicalizzazione

C. Appendix 3

Table 3 of keywords used in Italian

Basic religious terms	Islam/islamico/islamica/islamici/islamiche/musulmano/musulmana/musulmani/musulmane
Places of worship	Moschea/moschee/imam/ corano
Religious practices	Ramadan/eid festa del sacrificio eid al-fitr/eid al-adha/preghiera del venerdì/hijab/niqab/burqa/burkini/halal/sharia
Political issues / public debate	radicalizzazione/fondamentalismo/terrorismo/talebani islamofobia/velo/Islamizzazione

D. Appendix 4

Table 4 Codebook

Category	Description	Sub-codes	Sub-sub codes
Media Mentioned	References to media formats mentioned in the posts	TV talk show	
Call-to-Action	Statements placed at the end of a post that explicitly invite or urge the audience to take a specific action	Provocation for people to respond; Respond to the specific photo or video	
Moral Judgement	Statements that express moral or ethical judgment about people, groups, actions, or events	Negative evaluation of situations	Unfair practices; Controversial or undesirable scenes
		Positive value attribution	Citizen gratitude; Value-based justification
		Threat construction	Identifying individuals as danger to national security; Linking foreign funds to terrorism

		National/Cultural identity	Criticism of abandoning national identity; Defense of national/cultural identity
		Political criticism	Criticism of the left
		Humanitarian appeals	General humanitarian action; Protection of children; Protection of women
		Exclusionary stance	Religious intolerance; Religious persecution of Christians; Rejection of perceived religious encroachment
Emotional Expressions	Language expressing strong emotional reactions	Indignation; Opposition; Approval/enthusiasm; Disappointment/frustration; Rejection/denial	
Terminology on Islam	Terms used to refer to Islam	Islamophobia; Islam radicalisation; Islamic regime; Radical Islam; Islamic caliphate; Islamic propaganda; Sharia; Muslim Brotherhood; Taharrush gamea	
Metaphors	Use of metaphorical language shaping interpretation	General metaphors; War metaphor (immigration as war)	
Migration	Representation of migration and integration as social or political issues	Islamic immigration; Immigration policy; Immigration as a problem; Integration issue; Citizenship issue	
Europe's Transformation	Islam framed as a threat to European identity and values	Shift in threat perception; Islamisation	Threat to European values; Threat to democracy; Threat to Christianity; Threat of mosque construction; Threat to women's rights
Social Context	Everyday spaces where Islam is represented as visible	Mosque; Islamic centre; Swimming pools; Church; Square; Neighbourhoods; Urban periphery; Shops; Italian mosques; Italian hospitals; Sanctuaries/churches; City streets; Schools	
Quantification	Use of numbers to emphasise scale and urgency	Number of mosques; Number of children from Gaza; Number of people killed; Monetary quantification; Numerous Muslims; Numerous cases and events; Numerous churches converted into mosques; Biggest	

		mosque in Europe/Italy; Muslim student majority; First non-Muslim country	
Negative Lexicon	Words with negative connotations	Incitement to hatred; Shame; Danger	
Hooks (Opening Statements)	Starting impact sentence of the post that frames interpretation and guides audience reaction	Testimonies	Iranian activist testimony; Boulangerie owner's testimony; Testimonies from ex-Muslims
		Religious symbols/practices as offensive	
		Public recognition of Ramadan	
		Gender threat	Arranged marriages; Group sexual harassment/assault; Ideology towards Muslim women
		Mosque	Imam; Islamic centre
		Religion practices	Islamic veil; Halal diet; Arabic language
		Security & crime	Islamic fundamentalism; Association with radicalism; Terrorist organisations
		Geopolitical projection	Turkey's Non-European identity; Gaza (Child rescue/aid; Hamas); Iran (women's resistance; Violence by Islamic regime)
		Threat amplification	Socio-political religious imposition; Threats and insults; Uncontrolled Islamic immigration; Perception of Islamic/Arabic cities; Islamisation
		Policy & governance	EU funding allocation; Citizenship and immigration policy; Defence of national/cultural identity
Actors	Social and political actors organised by discursive role	Political actors	Politicians; The left; Socialist; Muslim politician; Mayor; Local municipality; Lega Nord; Islamic party
		Institutional actors	European institutions; Italian institutions; Austrian court; French intelligence
		Extremist actors	ISIS; Terrorist organisations; Islamic extremists; Islamic regimes; Khamenei
		Religious actors	Imams; Islamic representatives; Muslim people; Muslim men; Muslim women;

			Muslim students; Muslim girls and teenagers; Ex-Muslims
		Civic/social actors	Citizens; European people; English people; New English people
		Minorities	Foreigners; Migrants; Minorities
		Gendered actors	Women; Muslim women; Iranian women
		Children/family	Children; School children; Parents
		Professional actors	Teachers; Journalists; Shop owners; Companies
		Collective actors	Association representatives; Activists; Iranian activists; Animal rights activists
		Religious groups	Christians
		Military actors	Bersaglieri; Police force
		Geopolitical populations	Iranian people
Geographical Context	Spatial references organizing the threat across scales	National/Local (Italy)	Milan; Bologna; Rome; Naples; Padova; Modena; Sassuolo; Lissone; Monfalcone; Civitavecchia; Perugia; Trieste; Catanzaro; San Donà di Piave; Emilia-Romagna; Italy
		European context	Belgium; Molenbeek; Brussels; Vienna; Strasbourg; England
		Non-European/global	Tehran; Kabul; Damascus; Saudi Arabia; Turkey; Islamic nations
Us vs Them	Construction of opposition between in-group and out-group	Traditionalist Muslim identity; Us (Italians) vs Them	
Political Goals	Value, arguments, and goals of political activities	Women's rights issue; Security issue; Defence of Western/ (Italian) values	Ban of mosques; Ban of Islamic veil